

D3.1: Static Code Analysers and Formal Verification Methods (first version)

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Abstract

This deliverable outlines the foundational structure and early implementation of the static code analysis and formal verification framework under Task T3.1. The framework, bundled into the Static Code Analysis Module, employs advanced Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques to improve vulnerability detection accuracy while minimizing false positives across diverse programming environments. Formal verification methods test software against modeled safety properties, validating critical behavioral requirements, especially in concurrent and functional systems. Together with symbolic execution for comprehensive path analysis, these methods culminate in the Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG), which consolidates all testing efforts into a structured report that integrates into the RESCALE platform as a first step to the creation of a Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM).

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Scope & Contribution	8
1.2	Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities	8
1.3	Contribution to WP3 and Project Objectives	8
1.4	Document Structure	10
2	State of the Art Analysis	11
2.1	Erlang	11
2.2	Python	11
2.3	C/C++	12
2.4	Symbolic Execution	12
2.4.1	Symbolic Execution Techniques	12
2.4.1.1	Path Exploration	13
2.4.1.2	Constraint Handling and Optimization	14
2.4.1.3	State Management	15
2.4.1.4	Execution Strategies	15
2.4.1.5	Abstraction	16
2.4.1.6	Path Explosion Mitigation	17
2.4.1.7	Memory Modeling	17
2.4.1.8	Path Prioritization and Heuristics	18
2.4.2	Symbolic Execution Tools	18
3	Static Code Analysis Module	20
3.1	Architecture	20
3.2	Utilization	22
3.3	Toolbox Overview	23
4	Development of Static Code Analysers	24
4.1	SAVE-ME: Large Language Models for Static Code Vulnerability Analysis	24
4.1.1	CodeBERT	24
4.1.2	SAVE-ME	27
4.1.3	Integration Into the Static Analysis Module	29
4.1.4	Enhancements over Existing Solutions	30
4.2	SASTer: Static Application Security Tester	30
4.2.1	SASTer-GUI	30
4.2.1.1	Architecture	31
4.2.1.2	ML/DL Integration	33
4.2.1.3	Evaluation Results	33
4.2.2	SASTer-CLI	35
4.2.2.1	Architecture	36
4.2.2.2	Evaluation Results	36
4.2.3	Integration Into the Static Analysis Module	37
4.2.4	Enhancements over Existing Solutions	38
4.2.5	Limitations and Future Enhancements	39
4.3	Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE)	39
4.3.1	Core Components and Functionality	40
4.3.2	Considerations and Enhancements	41

4.4	Efforts Related to RefactorERL	41
5	Formal Verification	43
5.1	DetectEr	43
5.1.1	Hennessy–Milner Logic and Safety Properties	44
5.1.2	Application to a Software Update Mechanism	45
6	SSCG Design and Generation	47
6.1	Requirements	47
6.1.1	Test Reporting Format	48
6.1.2	Reproducible Testing	48
6.1.3	Classification of Artifacts	48
6.1.4	Classification of Vulnerabilities and Weaknesses	49
6.2	Initial Design	49
6.3	Unification of Test Reports	52
6.4	SARIF	53
6.4.1	Overview	53
6.4.2	Format Details	54
6.4.3	Context in RESCALE	55
6.4.4	SARIF Validation	56
6.4.5	Challenges in Using SARIF for SSCG	56
6.5	SSCG Generator	57
7	Main Innovations & Conclusion	59
7.1	Main Innovations	59
7.2	Conclusion	59
7.3	Future Work	60
7.3.1	Identified Challenges	60
7.3.2	Possible Mitigations & Improvements	61
	Appendices	62
A	SSCG Example	63
B	SARIF Examples	66
B.1	Simple Example	66
B.2	SAVE-ME Example	67
B.3	Bandit Example	68

List of Figures

1	RESCALE Components Architecture	9
2	Static Code Analysis Module Architecture	21
3	Static Code Analysis Module Utilization	22
4	An illustration about the replaced token detection objective. Source: [20].	26
5	Overview of the SAVE-ME architecture with pipeline	28
6	SASter Dashboard	34
7	SASter Analysis	34
8	SASter Results	35
9	SASter CLI	37
10	SSCG Concept	50
11	CycloneDX Attestations Overview	51
12	Unification of Analyzer Reports with an Example Set of Analyzers	53

List of Abbreviations

- API** Application Programming Interface. 19, 20, 32
- BERT** Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers. 24
- BOM** Bill of Materials. 10, 49
- CD** Continuous Development. 32, 37, 38, 52, 54, 56, 59
- CDX** CycloneDX. 10, 22, 49–52, 57
- CEGAR** Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement. 16
- CFG** Control Flow Graph. 39, 40
- CI** Continuous Integration. 20, 22, 32, 37, 38, 52, 54, 56, 59
- CLI** Command Line Interface. 20, 22, 35–38, 56, 57
- CVE** Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures. 49, 60, 61
- CWE** Common Weakness Enumeration. 49, 60, 61
- DL** Deep Learning. 1, 8–11, 14, 20, 23, 33, 38, 39, 41, 42, 52, 53, 59
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 9
- ELF** Executable and Linkable Format. 40
- GUI** Graphical User Interface. 30, 35, 38
- HML** Hennessy–Milner Logic. 23, 44
- IoT** Internet of Things. 45, 46
- IVEE** Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine. 9, 23, 39–41, 59
- JSF** JSON Signature Format. 52
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 21, 32, 36, 48, 51, 53, 54, 56, 57
- LLM** Large Language Model. 10, 24
- LLVM** Low-Level Virtual Machine. 19
- ML** Machine Learning. 1, 8–11, 20, 23, 33, 38, 39, 41, 42, 52, 53, 59
- MLM** Masked Language Modeling. 25
- MVP** Minimum Viable Product. 49

NIST National Institute of Standards and Technology. 56

NLP Natural language processing. 24

NVD National Vulnerability Database. 49

PE Portable Executable. 40

PKI Public Key Infrastructure. 52

RTD Replaced Token Detection. 25

SARIF Static Analysis Results Interchange Format. 31–33, 36–38, 48, 52–57, 59–61

SAST Static Application Security Testing. 30–32, 39

SAVE-ME Static Analysis of Vulnerabilities – Machine Learning Enhancements. 5, 24, 26–30

SBOM Software Bill of Materials. 9, 20, 22, 57, 59, 60

sHML safe Hennessy–Milner Logic. 43–45

SMT Satisfiability Modulo Theories. 14, 19

SotA State of the Art. 11, 12, 20

SSCG Static Supply Chain component Guarantee. 1, 8–10, 20–22, 47–52, 56–59

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 1, 8, 9, 21, 22, 47, 49, 57–59

VM Virtual Machine. 20

XML Extensible Markup Language. 32, 36, 48

1 Introduction

One of the primary goals of RESCALE is to improve static code analysis and formal verification methods. This includes developing advanced static code analyzers using Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques to enhance accuracy and reduce false positives. The respective task T3.1 also explores formal verification approaches to ensure software security, delivering a comprehensive framework - the RESCALE Static Code Analysis Module - for detecting vulnerabilities effectively. The outcome of the Static Code Analysis Module is then packaged as a Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG) and sent to other RESCALE infrastructure components which aggregate all information about a software artifact into a Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM).

1.1 Scope & Contribution

This document outlines the results of the first phase of task T3.1 "Static Code Analysis and Formal Verification". This phase involves in particular the initial design and prototypical implementation of static code analyzers, exploration of formal verification approaches, as well as the SSCG Generator and the overall construction and usability of the Static Code Analysis Module.

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

Deliverable D3.1 represents the first outcome of Task 3.1 within Work Package 3 (WP3) and is also pertinent to Work Packages 4 (WP4) and 5 (WP5). This deliverable describes the architecture and tooling associated with the Static Code Analysis Module, with specific integration aspects linked to WP5. Additionally, Task 3.1 defines the SSCG report, which is a first building block towards producing a TBOM in WP4.

1.3 Contribution to WP3 and Project Objectives

The RESCALE workflow consists of essentially three major steps leading to the creation of a TBOM. The very first step of the workflow is about an entity statically testing source code of a software project and assembling results and findings into a document called SSCG. This entity is called the 'Producer' in the context of RESCALE roles (see D2.5). Typically the Producer is in some way the 'owner' of the respective software project, for example a commercial organization which distributes the software as compiled package or the maintainer of an open source project. The static testing of source code happens within the Static Code Analysis Module which incorporates sets of different tools for different technology stacks. Based on a certain configuration these tools are executed on the source code of the software project. While many tools are generically executable on any source code of a specific programming language, there are also tools which need project specific configuration as further information is needed to test for certain characteristics of the software.

The resulting SSCG can be published by the Producer along a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) to the RESCALE infrastructure. Here it can be picked up by a different entity called the ‘Consumer’ (D2.5) of the software project for the second step of the RESCALE workflow, the dynamic testing (D3.3) which can also involve specific hardware testing (D3.5) and even interactions with operating system kernels (D3.7). Results of the dynamic testing are assembled into a Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee (DSCG) and also sent to the RESCALE infrastructure where finally the TBOM (D4.1) is created as the third and last step of the RESCALE workflow. In D2.5 a high level architecture was presented to reflect on this workflow (see figure 1).

Figure 1: RESCALE Components Architecture

T3.1 incorporates a range of Machine Learning (ML)/Deep Learning (DL) tools to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of vulnerability detection for software projects. Key tools include CodeBERT, which applies transformer-based models for source code analysis, and SAVE-ME, which fine-tunes CodeBERT for detecting specific vulnerabilities in Erlang code. Additionally, the SASTer tool combines ML-enhanced static analysis for Python and C/C++, reducing false positives and providing more precise insights into potential security issues.

Within RESCALE, formal verification is used in two different flavors, in the context of verification of execution traces and in the context of symbolic execution. For the verification of traces, the tool DetectEr is used. However, the main focus here is to create formal models which can be used for the actual verification of traces for the Erlang programming language. Regarding symbolic execution, a new tool based on the angr platform [70], the Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE), will be presented.

To streamline the user experience, the tooling is packaged as the Static Code Analysis Module with its own high level configuration. This configuration is directed towards the mentioned analyzers and also towards the SSCG Generator, which reflects on the results of the analyzers with respect to a targeted compliance standard. Throughout RESCALE, the Bill of Materials (BOM) structure as defined in ‘CycloneDX Bill of materials specification’ [19] is used (and extended if necessary) and hence the SSCG effectively maps test results and their relation to configurable standards into a CycloneDX (CDX) document. It is also desirable to create a unified test output which takes the results of all tooling into consideration as part of the SSCG. Initial approaches to this problem will be presented.

Also there is the aspect of assurance of the execution of the Static Code Analysis Module being trustworthy. Without any cryptographic guarantees it is easy for the Producer entity to forge test results or tinker with meta information in the SSCG. This overall topic is quite underdeveloped at the current time but this document still attempts to present the related problems.

1.4 Document Structure

Each chapter of the main body of this document is focused on distinct components and methods. Chapter 3 covers the architecture and utilization of the Static Code Analysis Module, which contains the static analysis tooling and makes it usable in a streamlined way. Chapter 4 shifts to the development of static code analyzers, particularly exploring ML/DL methods, including the use of large language models (LLMs), and symbolic execution methods. This chapter also details specific approaches, providing insight into how new techniques are being integrated to improve upon existing solutions.

Subsequent chapters introduce formal verification techniques (Chapter 5) and SSCG design and generation processes (Chapter 6). Each of these chapters is structured to include requirements, design considerations, and practical applications, thereby offering a comprehensive view of the technologies and their alignment with project goals. The final chapters address a summarizing conclusion (Chapter 7) that captures the document’s key insights, presented innovations and future work.

2 State of the Art Analysis

Throughout the project the languages Erlang, Python and C/C++ are used for static code analysis. The following paragraphs provide a recap and analysis of the respective state of the art as outlined in D2.3. Further the SotA of symbolic execution methods is described in depth.

2.1 Erlang

Erlang’s static analysis ecosystem, featuring tools like Dialyzer [1], Xref [2], Elvis [32], RefactorErl [8] and InfERL [27], provides essential capabilities for detecting code discrepancies, enforcing style guidelines, and identifying unused code. Despite these benefits, these tools often generate a lot of false positives or findings that are not of any special interest, making it challenging for developers to prioritize critical issues. They also struggle to uncover more intricate security vulnerabilities and complex bugs that may arise in the language’s concurrent and distributed environment. ML/DL methods have so far not been applied to static code analysis for Erlang.

Formal verification tools, such as McErlang [24] and Concuerror [26], support model checking and concurrency analysis but face scalability issues and require significant expertise, limiting their broader adoption. Although formal verification is crucial for the reliability of critical applications, existing tools still struggle with Erlang’s dynamic behavior and concurrency model, highlighting the need for different approaches that integrate seamlessly into the development process. Another formal verification tool, Detector [4], will be utilized in RESCALE and is discussed in this document, as it partially addresses some of these problems, even though it was initially overlooked in D2.3.

2.2 Python

Python’s static analysis ecosystem is well-established, featuring a range of techniques designed to enforce code quality, detect errors, identify vulnerabilities and ensure compliance with coding standards. However, Python’s dynamic nature presents unique challenges for static analysis. Traditional approaches often struggle with the dynamic typing system and runtime behaviors such as duck typing and late binding. These characteristics can lead to a higher incidence of false positives, making it difficult for developers to prioritize critical issues effectively.

Recent advancements have sought to address these challenges through symbolic execution and type inference techniques, which aim to provide a more precise analysis of Python code. Despite these improvements, analyzing Python’s dynamic features, such as metaprogramming and runtime type modifications, remains an open problem. Additionally, runtime features like dynamic attribute addition and the use of “eval” or “exec” introduce unpredictable behaviors that static analysis tools find challenging to model accurately. Machine learning methods have been introduced to improve defect prediction and pattern recognition, but their adoption in static code analysis for Python is still in its infancy, particularly when compared to traditional rule-based systems. For instance, ML-based techniques have shown promise in identifying patterns and anomalies, though they require extensive training data and can produce less interpretable

results compared to rule-based methods.

2.3 C/C++

C and C++ are among the most widely analyzed languages due to their extensive use in critical systems and their susceptibility to vulnerabilities like buffer overflows, memory leaks, and undefined behaviors. The static analysis of C and C++ code typically relies on techniques such as control flow analysis, data flow analysis, and abstract interpretation. These methods provide a robust foundation for detecting common bugs and ensuring compliance with best practices.

However, these techniques face challenges in handling C/C++'s complex features, including manual memory management, extensive use of macros, and undefined behaviors. Additionally, concurrency issues and low-level hardware interactions in C/C++ systems complicate static analysis. Formal methods, such as model checking and symbolic execution, have been applied to C/C++ to improve the detection of race conditions and ensure the correctness of safety-critical systems. Despite their effectiveness, these methods often face scalability issues due to the languages' inherent complexity and low-level nature.

Emerging techniques, including the integration of machine learning for anomaly detection and predictive analysis, aim to complement traditional methods. However, their effectiveness is often limited by the need for large datasets and the challenge of interpreting results in the context of security-critical applications. This highlights the need for continuous development of hybrid approaches that leverage the strengths of both traditional and modern methods to improve static code analysis for C and C++ programs.

2.4 Symbolic Execution

Symbolic execution is a powerful technique in static code analysis that explores program paths to identify vulnerabilities. In this section, we explore various symbolic execution techniques used to enhance the analysis process, followed by key SotA tools that implement symbolic execution. This section provides an extensive exploration of symbolic execution techniques because D2.3 only partially addresses the subject, leaving significant gaps in the depth and detail of its coverage.

2.4.1 Symbolic Execution Techniques

Symbolic execution is a cornerstone of static code analysis, enabling the exploration of all feasible program paths to detect vulnerabilities, errors and other software issues. This powerful technique operates by treating inputs as symbolic variables rather than concrete values, allowing multiple execution paths to be analyzed simultaneously. Through systematic path exploration, symbolic execution can uncover complex, path-dependent bugs that traditional testing methods might overlook.

Despite its strengths, symbolic execution faces significant challenges, such as path explosion, constraint-solving complexity and handling interactions with external systems. Over the years,

various techniques have been developed to address these limitations, enhancing its scalability, precision and efficiency. However, it is important to note that no universally agreed-upon taxonomy of symbolic execution techniques currently exists. The classification of techniques often depends on the context of their application, which can vary across different tools and research studies.

Several comprehensive surveys have contributed to the understanding and evolution of symbolic execution. For instance, Baldoni et al. [5], provide an extensive survey of symbolic execution techniques, highlighting their applications and limitations. Additionally the survey of Yang et al. [83] explores recent developments in symbolic execution, focusing on innovative strategies to improve efficiency and scalability. While these surveys are comprehensive, they do not cover all techniques or their diverse applications, highlighting the need for continued exploration and categorization.

This section organizes symbolic execution techniques into categories based on their objectives and applications. Each subsection delves into specific methods, offering a structured approach to understanding how symbolic execution can be utilized for software analysis.

2.4.1.1 Path Exploration

In symbolic execution, path exploration is a fundamental process that involves systematically traversing all possible execution paths of a program. This comprehensive analysis enables the detection of potential errors, vulnerabilities and ensures thorough testing by considering various input scenarios. However, the exponential growth of execution paths, known as the path explosion problem, poses significant challenges. To address this, several techniques have been developed to optimize path exploration and manage computational resources effectively. These techniques are described below in detail:

- **Path Pruning:** This technique involves eliminating infeasible or redundant paths during exploration. By applying heuristics or static analysis, symbolic execution can focus on paths that are more likely to reveal errors, thereby reducing the overall number of paths to explore. For instance, the work by Chen et al. [14] introduces dynamic path pruning strategies to enhance the efficiency of symbolic execution. Another paper by Molina et al. [48] discusses techniques for pruning infeasible paths to enhance the efficiency of symbolic execution.
- **Path Merging:** Path merging combines similar execution paths into a single path when they converge at a program point. This approach reduces redundancy and the number of paths that need to be analyzed. Techniques like state merging and value summaries are employed to facilitate this process. The study by Kuznetsov et al. [40] presents an efficient state merging method in symbolic execution. Another study by Sen et al. [69] introduces MultiSE, which uses value summaries to enable efficient path merging in multi-path symbolic execution, effectively reducing redundant execution and improving performance.
- **Depth-Bounded Search:** To prevent infinite or excessively deep recursion during path exploration, depth-bounded search limits the depth of exploration. By setting a maximum depth, this technique ensures that the analysis remains tractable and avoids getting

stuck in deep or infinite loops. The work by Singh et al. [71] introduces test-depth partitioning, which inherently applies depth limitations to improve the scalability of symbolic execution.

- **Loop Unrolling and Bounding:** Loops can lead to an infinite number of execution paths. Loop unrolling involves expanding the loop a fixed number of times, while loop bounding sets a limit on the number of iterations to explore. These techniques help in managing loops during symbolic execution, making the analysis more feasible. The work by Baldoni et al. [5] discusses various strategies, including loop unrolling, to handle loops in symbolic execution. In their work, Jaffar et al. [34] introduce unbounded symbolic execution for program verification, focusing on abstracting loops to enable termination while refining these abstractions to avoid false positives.

Path exploration techniques optimize symbolic execution by focusing on critical execution paths. These strategies help mitigate resource consumption, enabling scalable analysis of extensive codebases.

2.4.1.2 Constraint Handling and Optimization

Constraints represent the conditions under which specific execution paths are feasible. Efficiently managing and solving these constraints is crucial for the scalability and effectiveness of symbolic execution. Several techniques have been developed to optimize constraint handling, ensuring that the analysis remains tractable even for complex programs:

- **Incremental Constraint Solving:** Incremental constraint involves solving constraints incrementally as new conditions are encountered during execution. By reusing previously computed solutions and only solving for the new constraints, incremental solving reduces computational overhead. In [42], Li et al., investigate how optimization techniques applied to Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) solvers can significantly improve symbolic execution performance by reducing constraint-solving time. Another work by Wen et al. [80], explores the integration of DL methods to enhance constraint-solving efficiency. Their method leverages predictive models to expedite solving, enabling faster symbolic execution. Lastly, Luo et al. [44] propose a time prediction model for constraint solving. This allows the symbolic execution engine to prioritize constraints based on expected solving times, optimizing performance and resource utilization.
- **Constraint Caching:** To avoid redundant computations, constraint caching stores the results of previously solved constraints. When the same or similar constraints are encountered again, the cached results can be reused, enhancing efficiency. The work by Shuai et al. introduces a partial solution-based caching mechanism in symbolic execution. This approach leverages partial solutions during constraint solving to improve the effectiveness of caching, significantly optimizing symbolic execution performance.
- **Constraint Simplification:** Simplifying constraints before solving them can lead to faster resolution times. Techniques such as constant folding, dead code elimination, and algebraic simplification are employed to reduce the complexity of constraints. In their survey of symbolic execution techniques Baldoni et al. [5] provide an overview of constraint simplification methods used in symbolic execution.

- **Lazy Initialization:** This strategy delays the creation of symbolic variables until they are actually needed during execution. By postponing the initialization of variables, the technique reduces the number of constraints generated, thereby optimizing performance. The paper by Braione et al. [9] explores lazy initialization in the context of symbolic execution and focuses on refining lazy initialization techniques due to their limitations.

Efficient constraint-solving techniques are crucial for managing symbolic execution's computational complexity. By reducing constraint-solving overhead, these methods enhance scalability and allow the analysis to handle intricate program logic effectively.

2.4.1.3 State Management

Effective state management is crucial to handle the potentially vast number of program states that arise during analysis. Efficiently managing these states ensures scalability and prevents resource exhaustion. Several techniques have been developed to optimize state management in symbolic execution:

- **State Subsumption:** This technique involves identifying and discarding program states that have already been explored or are equivalent to previously encountered states. By recognizing when a new state is subsumed by an existing one, symbolic execution can avoid redundant analysis, thereby enhancing efficiency. The work by Anand et al. [3] introduces a method for examining whether a symbolic state is subsumed by another during execution, effectively pruning the state space.
- **State Merging:** State merging combines multiple program states that have reached the same point in the program with similar conditions. By merging these states, symbolic execution reduces the number of paths to explore, mitigating the path explosion problem. The study by Kuznetsov et al. [40] presents an efficient state merging technique in symbolic execution.
- **State Caching and Reuse:** This approach involves storing previously encountered program states and reusing them when the same or similar states are encountered again. By caching these states, symbolic execution can avoid redundant computations, improving overall efficiency. The research by Sen et al. [69] discusses the implementation of state caching mechanisms in symbolic execution and their impact on performance.

State subsumption and caching mechanisms prevent resource exhaustion by managing program states dynamically. These techniques ensure symbolic execution remains practical for larger codebases.

2.4.1.4 Execution Strategies

Various strategies have been developed to enhance efficiency and scalability in symbolic execution. These strategies guide the execution process, focusing on critical parts of the program and managing resources effectively. Key execution strategies include the ones explained below:

- **Dynamic Symbolic Execution:** Also known as dynamic symbolic testing, this approach combines symbolic execution with runtime information to handle dynamic behaviors and external interactions. By adapting to the runtime context, it improves path coverage and uncovers complex bugs. Concolic execution or hybrid execution is a specific form of dynamic symbolic execution. It runs the program with concrete inputs while simultaneously performing symbolic analysis. This hybrid method is particularly effective for generating inputs that expose subtle bugs. The work by Yun et al. [84], introduces QSYM, an optimized concolic execution engine designed for hybrid fuzzing, addressing performance bottlenecks in traditional concolic execution. Another study by Jaffar et al. [33], presents a novel system that uses interpolation techniques to tackle the path explosion problem, enhancing the scalability of dynamic symbolic execution. Lastly, Vishnyakov et al. [79] highlights performance improvements in dynamic symbolic execution by optimizing symbolic formula simplification and skipping non-symbolic instructions, demonstrating superior efficiency.
- **Selective Symbolic Execution:** This strategy focuses symbolic execution on specific parts of the program, such as functions or modules that are critical or prone to errors. By narrowing the scope, it reduces computational overhead and enhances scalability. The study by He et al. presents a technique for selective symbolic execution, targeting specific program components to improve efficiency [28].

Execution strategies are critical for balancing the thoroughness of analysis with computational efficiency. These strategies tailor symbolic execution to prioritize paths most likely to reveal significant insights.

2.4.1.5 Abstraction

Abstraction techniques are employed to simplify complex program structures and data, making analysis more tractable. By abstracting certain elements, these techniques reduce the state space and computational overhead, enhancing the efficiency of symbolic execution. Some abstraction techniques are explained below in detail:

- **Predicate Abstraction:** This method abstracts program states by mapping them to a finite set of boolean expressions, known as predicates. By focusing on these predicates, the analysis becomes more manageable. The work by Jonáš et al. [35] introduces a technique that combines symbolic execution with predicate abstraction and Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement (CEGAR) to improve the effectiveness of symbolic execution in proving unreachability.
- **Symbolic Summarization:** Symbolic summarization involves creating concise representations of program components, such as functions or loops, capturing their behavior without delving into detailed execution paths. This technique allows symbolic execution to handle complex programs more efficiently by focusing on high-level summaries. The study by Boudhiba et al. [7] presents a method for symbolic execution of transition systems using function summaries, which are logical formulas built from concrete values describing representative input and output data tuples of the function.

- **Interpolant Generation:** Interpolant generation is used to derive intermediate assertions, known as interpolants, that summarize the effect of a sequence of program statements. These interpolants help in refining abstractions and guiding the symbolic execution process. The study by Jaffar et al., mentioned in subsection 2.4.1.4 [33], which introduced TracerX, was build using interpolation to address the path explosion problem.

Abstraction techniques simplify complex program behaviors, improving both the precision and performance of symbolic execution. This allows for a broader application of symbolic execution in complex system analysis.

2.4.1.6 Path Explosion Mitigation

The path explosion problem arises when the number of execution paths grows exponentially due to program complexity, loops and conditionals. This rapid growth can overwhelm computational resources, making exhaustive analysis impractical. Several mitigation techniques have been developed designed to tackle this specific issue faced in symbolic execution:

- **Parallel Path Exploration:** This technique involves distributing the exploration of execution paths across multiple processors or machines. By parallelizing the workload, symbolic execution can handle a larger number of paths simultaneously, reducing the time required for analysis. The work by Karna et al. [37] introduces a parallel symbolic execution framework that effectively distributes path exploration tasks, enhancing scalability. Additionally, Ryan et al., [65] propose a modular approach where independent components of hardware designs are explored separately and reused, effectively addressing path explosion through parallel composition strategies.
- **Work Stealing:** In dynamic parallel execution environments, work stealing allows idle processors to take over tasks from busy processors. This load-balancing strategy ensures efficient utilization of computational resources during symbolic execution. The study by Wen et al. [81] presents a work-stealing scheduler designed for parallel symbolic execution, demonstrating significant performance improvements.

Tackling path explosion is vital for symbolic execution's success in real-world scenarios. Techniques like selective exploration ensure that computational resources are allocated efficiently without compromising analysis depth.

2.4.1.7 Memory Modeling

Accurately modeling memory in symbolic execution is crucial for analyzing programs that utilize complex data structures and pointer manipulations. Effective memory modeling ensures that symbolic execution can handle various memory operations, including dynamic allocations and pointer arithmetic. Some techniques are analyzed below:

- **Precise Memory Modeling:** This approach aims to accurately represent the program's memory state, including complex data structures and pointer relationships. By maintaining a detailed model of memory, symbolic execution can precisely track variable values

and detect subtle errors. Borzacchiello et al., [6] discuss key ideas and new thoughts on memory models in symbolic execution, highlighting the importance of precise memory modeling.

- **Simplified Memory Models:** To improve performance, some symbolic execution tools use simplified memory models that abstract certain details of the memory state. While this can enhance scalability, it may reduce the precision of the analysis. Kapus et al., [36] presented a segmented memory model for symbolic execution, which reduces forking due to symbolic pointer dereferences, often completely, thereby decreasing execution time and memory usage.

Effective memory modeling enables symbolic execution to handle dynamic data structures and low-level operations. This extends the applicability of symbolic execution to programs with complex memory interactions, ensuring thorough analysis.

2.4.1.8 Path Prioritization and Heuristics

Efficiently exploring the vast number of possible execution paths is crucial. Path prioritization and heuristics guide the exploration process, focusing on paths that are more likely to uncover errors or achieve higher code coverage. Key strategies include:

- **Coverage-Guided Execution:** This approach prioritizes paths that are expected to increase code coverage, ensuring that untested parts of the program are explored. By focusing on less-explored paths, this heuristic enhances the thoroughness of testing. The study by Cha et al. [13] introduces a technique that automatically generates search heuristics for dynamic symbolic execution, improving coverage by learning from previous explorations.
- **Bug-Focused Heuristics:** These heuristics prioritize paths that are more likely to contain bugs, such as those involving complex conditions or known vulnerable patterns. By directing exploration towards these paths, the efficiency of bug detection is enhanced. The research by Ruaro et al. [64] presents SyML, a system that guides symbolic execution toward vulnerable states through pattern learning, effectively focusing on bug-prone paths.

Guided by heuristics, path prioritization enhances symbolic execution by targeting paths likely to reveal vulnerabilities. This approach streamlines the analysis and accelerates vulnerability detection.

2.4.2 Symbolic Execution Tools

Symbolic execution has led to the development of various tools designed to analyze and test software systems. These tools differ in their capabilities, target platforms and applications. Below is an overview of some prominent symbolic execution tools:

- **KLEE**: Built on the Low-Level Virtual Machine (LLVM) compiler infrastructure, KLEE is an open-source symbolic execution engine that automatically generates high-coverage tests for complex systems programs [10]. It has been instrumental in detecting bugs and verifying software correctness.
- **Manticore**: Developed by Trail of Bits [55], Manticore is a symbolic execution tool capable of analyzing smart contracts and binaries [53]. It offers features like program exploration, input generation, error discovery and a programmatic interface via a Python API.
- **Maat**: Also from Trail of Bits [55], Maat is an open-source dynamic symbolic execution and binary analysis framework [54]. It provides functionalities such as symbolic execution, taint analysis, constraint solving, binary loading and environment simulation. Maat leverages Ghidra's SLEIGH library for assembly lifting.
- **Triton**: Triton is a dynamic binary analysis framework that provides robust symbolic execution capabilities [66]. It supports taint analysis, dynamic symbolic execution and program analysis for binary-level programs.
- **Angr**: Angr is a powerful binary analysis platform that combines symbolic execution with other analysis techniques like CFG recovery, taint analysis and more [21]. It's widely used for vulnerability discovery in complex binaries.
- **CrossHair**: CrossHair is an analysis tool for Python that blurs the line between testing and type systems [75]. It works by repeatedly calling functions with symbolic inputs, using an SMT solver to explore viable execution paths and find counterexamples. CrossHair supports symbolic reasoning for built-in types, user-defined classes and much of the standard library, making it a comprehensive tool for Python code analysis.
- **Sydr**: Sydr is a dynamic symbolic execution tool that combines DynamoRIO dynamic binary instrumentation with the Triton symbolic engine. It introduces performance and accuracy improvements, such as skipping non-symbolic instructions and path predicate slicing, to enhance symbolic execution efficiency.
- **Symbooglix**: Symbooglix is a symbolic execution tool for Boogie programs, facilitating the analysis and verification of programs written in the Boogie intermediate verification language [43].
- **OSS-Sydr-Fuzz**: OSS-Sydr-Fuzz is a hybrid fuzzing tool for open-source software that combines symbolic execution with fuzzing techniques to improve vulnerability detection [76].

These tools exemplify the diverse applications of symbolic execution in software analysis, testing and verification. They cater to various programming languages, platforms and analysis needs, contributing significantly to the advancement of software reliability and security.

3 Static Code Analysis Module

The RESCALE static code analysis module processes software projects, specifically their source code and the SBOM associated with it, to identify and assess potential security vulnerabilities and weaknesses. It employs advanced ML and DL enhanced static code analyzers, which go beyond traditional methods to detect issues more effectively. The ML/DL components play a crucial role in reducing false positives, enhancing the accuracy of the analysis compared to traditional static analysis tools.

A key benefit of this module is that it aggregates these analyzers in a unified way. In the current State of the Art (SotA), every static code analysis tool typically needs to be handled uniquely since there is no standardized Application Programming Interface (API), which complicates the evaluation process. By providing a streamlined interface, the RESCALE module simplifies interaction with various analyzers, enhancing user experience and efficiency.

Reflecting on the envisioned workflows from D2.5, RESCALE will initially design this module as a container, making it compatible with common Continuous Integration (CI) systems. Within these CI systems, source code typically gets injected at runtime, allowing the module to automatically assess the code as part of the development pipeline. While the module is designed to be containerized for easy integration, its architecture remains independent of the containerized approach, ensuring flexibility and adaptability for various deployment environments (for example using a Virtual Machine (VM) based approach).

The outcome of the analysis is the SSCG, a detailed report that includes the types of tests performed, their results, the identity of the evaluator, the version of the assessed asset etc. The SSCG is generated using a newly developed piece of software, the SSCG Generator, and it can be published to the management module for further processing or just stored locally for inspection without exposing information to the public.

3.1 Architecture

Figure 2 outlines the architecture of the RESCALE static code analysis module, highlighting its self-contained design and integration with key components. The process starts with the Software Repository, containing the source code and the SBOM. Configuration Management sets up the container runtime environment based on specified settings, and the Execution Engine initiates the static code analysis using the configured analyzers.

A key feature of this module is its ability to aggregate multiple static analyzers. Each analyzer is enclosed in a RESCALE Wrapper, which provides a standardized interface. In its simplest form, the RESCALE Wrapper might just be a shell script that carries the name of the targeted static code analyzer, offering a Command Line Interface (CLI) to start the analyzer with a default set of options. This approach addresses the common issue of handling each static analysis tool uniquely due to the lack of standardized APIs. It might be of interest later on to augment this API with additional capabilities to stop the analysis or track its progress.

While RESCALE hasn't yet settled on a specific test output format, the wrapper must transform the analyzer's output to include how the analyzer was invoked, ensuring reproducibility of

Figure 2: Static Code Analysis Module Architecture

findings. It also needs to detail the vulnerabilities and weaknesses identified, which is crucial for supporting the TBOM lifecycle as explained in D4.1, where a score-based process is used to evaluate the status of an asset with a TBOM. Additionally, the wrapper should attach a more detailed report about the code locations and how different findings might relate to each other, enhancing the depth of analysis.

The wrapper output is expected to be in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, aligning with the SSCG’s design as a JSON document. This consistency in format simplifies the integration of outputs into the overall analysis process and facilitates further processing.

The module uses an initial set of configuration parameters (given as environment variables) to manage the analysis process. These parameters are likely subject to change during WP5 integration activities.

- **USER_ACCESS_TOKEN**: A user access token for secure communication with the RESCALE Management Module (e.g., “abc123token”). This token is processed by the SSCG Generator, which acts as a client of the management module, ensuring that only authorized users can publish analysis results.
- **LANG_INFO**: Specifies the programming languages used in the source code (e.g., “Python 3.10, Erlang 24, C11”). The Execution Engine maintains a mapping between this information and the respective analyzers, ensuring that the correct tools are used for each language (or technology) specified in the configuration.
- **SRC_PATH**: A list of source code file locations (e.g., “./src/*”). This parameter guides the module to the directories where the source code is located, allowing it to identify the files to be analyzed.
- **DRY_RUN**: A flag to control whether the analysis is a “dry run” (e.g., “true” or “false”). When set to “true,” the analysis results are stored locally without publishing to the RESCALE Management Module. When set to “false,” the module can publish the results, depending on the configuration.

- **SBOM_PATH**: The location of the SBOM file (e.g., “/path/to/sbom”). This path provides the necessary input for the analysis, allowing the module to use the SBOM in conjunction with the source code for a comprehensive evaluation.

After executing the static analysis, the results are sent to the SSCG Generator, where the SSCG, formatted as a CDX document (as discussed in D4.1), is compiled. Afterwards, the CycloneDX CLI tool [56] validates the SSCG to ensure its compliance with the CycloneDX specification. Depending on the module configuration, the SSCG Generator will either publish the SSCG to the RESCALE Management Module or store it locally as a CI artifact during a dry run, preserving privacy and control over the information.

3.2 Utilization

Figure 3 illustrates the utilization of the RESCALE static code analysis module within a producer test infrastructure, showing how various components interact to enable the analysis of source code and the generation of an SSCG. The process begins with the download or update of the static code analysis module from the module repository, ensuring it is up-to-date with the latest analyzer updates. Then, configuration settings are ingested to define parameters for the analysis, such as programming language settings. The source code, optional other assets subject to static testing (like compiled binaries), and the SBOM which is stored in the code repository, are injected into the static code analysis module, which processes these inputs to identify vulnerabilities and weaknesses and generates the SSCG with relevant details. Once the SSCG is generated, it can be published to the management module for further processing towards the TBOM. In the case of a dry run, the SSCG can be kept locally within the producer’s test infrastructure without being published.

Figure 3: Static Code Analysis Module Utilization

This approach offers several advantages. First, it allows for the use of a generic static code analysis module that can be applied to any software under test, regardless of the programming language or its version. While it may still be beneficial to create specialized modules for different programming languages to optimize the analysis, the generic module provides a flexible and versatile solution. Additionally, the module is compatible with existing CI infrastructure,

enabling seamless integration into current development workflows without the need for extensive changes or adaptations. An approach involving static code analysis modules specific to the software being tested is not feasible, as it would require the RESCALE infrastructure to generate such modules on demand for each software project.

3.3 Toolbox Overview

The Static Code Analysis Module incorporates several tools to deliver security insights across multiple programming languages, enhanced with ML/DL capabilities to reduce false positives, prioritize findings, and improve code coverage.

SASter, a bundle of static analysis tools, is tailored for Python and C/C++. It leverages machine learning to identify security issues and other problems in the codebase under analysis.

Further RESCALE project leverages CodeBERT, a transformer-based language model adapted to code, to enhance vulnerability detection by understanding complex code structures and relationships. SAVE-ME, a new tool developed in RESCALE, builds upon CodeBERT, fine-tuning it specifically for identifying vulnerabilities in Erlang code.

DetectEr is a runtime verification tool for Erlang, designed to monitor system behaviors and detect concurrency issues like race conditions. Utilizing Hennessy–Milner Logic (HML), DetectEr specifies safety properties and validates system actions against these properties in real-time, without the need for exhaustive formal verification, offering a pragmatic way of error detection under real-world conditions. Within RESCALE there will be safety properties developed for e.g., a software update mechanism.

The Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE) in RESCALE leverages symbolic execution to provide a thorough assessment of software components, going beyond standard syntactical analysis. By systematically exploring all possible execution paths with symbolic inputs, IVEE verifies code against specified properties, identifying vulnerabilities that conventional tools may overlook. Built on the angr platform, IVEE benefits from angr’s capabilities for analyzing binary code and navigating complex control flows, making it effective in assessing compiled applications and low-level vulnerabilities.

Each of these tools is described in greater detail in their respective sections later in the document.

4 Development of Static Code Analysers

Traditional static analysis tools for detecting vulnerabilities in source code often rely on rule-based approaches or pattern matching. While these methods can identify certain types of vulnerabilities – here broadly referring to weaknesses, deficiencies, or other issues in code – they are limited by their predefined rules and struggle with the complexity and evolving nature of modern programming languages. Additionally, static analysis tools often fail to capture subtle issues that arise from context-dependent code behavior, which is particularly important in functional and concurrent programming languages like Erlang.

This section describes two approaches for static analysis within RESCALE: Static Analysis of Vulnerabilities – Machine Learning Enhancements (SAVE-ME) based on Large Language Models (LLMs) (Section 4.1), and Static Application Security Tester (SASter), a modular extensible platform for streamlining the process of analyzing source code (Section 4.2). In addition, our initial efforts regarding RefactorERL, an advanced tool designed for static analysis and refactoring of Erlang code, are discussed in Section 4.4.

4.1 SAVE-ME: Large Language Models for Static Code Vulnerability Analysis

Large Language Models (LLMs) such as CodeBERT [20] offer a powerful alternative and enhancement to traditional static code analysis tools. LLMs can be pretrained on large amounts of source code to learn both syntax and semantic structures, allowing them to recognize a broader range of vulnerabilities and patterns that go beyond simple rule-based detection. By fine-tuning these models on specific datasets, we can enhance their ability to identify security vulnerabilities in a given language.

For this part of the Static Code Analysis Module, we focus on classifying vulnerabilities in Erlang source code. Erlang’s unique features introduce specific security challenges that are not as prevalent in other languages. Traditional static analysis tools may not be fully equipped to handle these challenges, making a machine learning-based approach like CodeBERT particularly valuable. Our tool, called Static Analysis of Vulnerabilities – Machine Learning Enhancements (SAVE-ME), is based on an LLM architecture, specifically CodeBERT.

4.1.1 CodeBERT

CodeBERT is a transformer-based model designed specifically for source code understanding. It is based on the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [17] architecture, which was originally designed for natural language processing (NLP). The transformer architecture forms the backbone of CodeBERT and is highly suited for processing structured data like source code because of its ability to model long-range dependencies and capture contextual information in a bidirectional manner.

Key components of the transformer architecture are the following:

- At the heart of the transformer is the self-attention mechanism, which allows the model to weigh the importance of each token (word or code token) relative to the others in the input sequence. A token is a unit of text, such as a word, symbol, or code element, that the model uses as its smallest building block for analysis. For source code, tokens include keywords (e.g., if, else), operators, identifiers, and even special characters or delimiters. The process of tokenization involves breaking down the input code into these discrete components, allowing the model to systematically process and analyze the sequence. This is important for understanding source code because dependencies between variables or function calls can occur at different parts of the code, often far apart. The self-attention mechanism allows CodeBERT to capture these dependencies and contextual relationships effectively.
- CodeBERT's transformer model is bidirectional, meaning it processes the entire input sequence in both directions (left-to-right and right-to-left). For code understanding, this is particularly beneficial because it enables the model to understand the relationships between code tokens, function names, arguments, and control flow structures, leading to more robust representations of code.
- CodeBERT breaks down source code into tokens and embeds them into high-dimensional vectors. This embedding captures both syntactic and semantic information, allowing the model to learn the relationships between keywords, variables, and operations.

The choice of a transformer architecture is motivated by its ability to process complex, structured data efficiently.

CodeBERT employs two pre-training objectives, the Masked Language Modeling (MLM) and the Replaced Token Detection (RTD):

- **Masked Language Modeling (MLM):** In this objective, a random subset of token positions is selected in both natural language (NL, e.g., code documentation) and programming language (PL) sequences. These positions are replaced with a special mask token. The model is then trained to predict the original tokens that were masked, enabling it to learn contextual representations of the input sequences.
- **Masked Language Modeling (MLM):** For this objective, some tokens in the original NL and PL sequences are randomly masked. A generator model, which is similar to an n-gram probabilistic model, replaces the masked tokens with predictions. Subsequently, a discriminator model is trained to identify whether a given token is the original token or a replacement. This task is framed as a binary classification problem. Both NL and code generators are language models, which generate plausible tokens for masked positions based on surrounding contexts. NL-Code discriminator is the targeted pre-trained model, which is trained via detecting plausible alternatives tokens sampled from NL and PL generators. NL-Code discriminator is used for producing general-purpose representations in the fine-tuning step. Both NL and code generators are thrown out in the fine-tuning step [20]. An illustration of RTD is shown in Figure 4.

CodeBERT's architecture is particularly suited for downstream tasks like vulnerability classification because of its pre-training objectives and modular design. During pre-training, CodeBERT learns to predict masked tokens and identify relationships between code snippets, equipping it with a deep understanding of syntax and semantics across multiple languages. This

Figure 4: An illustration about the replaced token detection objective.

Source: [20].

capability makes it ideal for tasks that require contextual reasoning, such as identifying vulnerabilities where syntactic patterns alone are insufficient. For example, vulnerabilities may stem from how a variable interacts across different scopes or how a function handles specific inputs, which CodeBERT’s bidirectional attention mechanism can effectively capture.

Training deep models like CodeBERT from scratch requires a vast amount of data and computational resources, especially when dealing with code from a less common language like Erlang. Transfer learning provides an efficient alternative. CodeBERT has been pre-trained on a large corpus of source code across multiple programming languages, allowing it to learn general representations of code structure and syntax. By fine-tuning the pre-trained model on our specific task – vulnerability classification in Erlang functions – we can leverage the knowledge CodeBERT has already learned, reducing the amount of data and time needed for training.

Fine-tuning CodeBERT involves adding a classification head on top of the pre-trained model and training it using labeled data. This process adjusts the model’s weights to optimize performance on the specific task, in this case, detecting vulnerabilities in Erlang code.

Erlang’s functional and concurrent programming paradigms pose unique challenges for static analysis tools, as they often require understanding non-linear data flows and message-passing patterns. CodeBERT mitigates these challenges by embedding Erlang functions into high-dimensional vector spaces that capture both syntactic and semantic information. These embeddings serve as a foundation for downstream classification, where patterns indicative of vulnerabilities can be identified with high accuracy.

Additionally, CodeBERT’s modularity allows it to be adapted for other use cases beyond classification. For example, it can be fine-tuned for code summarization, code search, or bug detection, showcasing its versatility and potential as a robust tool for various code analysis tasks. By leveraging CodeBERT, SAVE-ME inherits these strengths and focuses them on the critical task of identifying security vulnerabilities in Erlang code, filling a significant gap left by traditional static analysis tools.

4.1.2 SAVE-ME

Static Analysis of Vulnerabilities – Machine Learning Enhancements (SAVE-ME) is an adaptation of the CodeBERT model specifically fine-tuned to detect insecure code patterns in Erlang. The model operates at the function level, making it suitable for analyzing individual Erlang functions in isolation, a critical capability given Erlang’s functional programming paradigm and its emphasis on concurrent processes.

To create SAVE-ME, we extend CodeBERT by integrating a task-specific classification head tailored for vulnerability detection. This modification enables the model to classify each function as either vulnerable or non-vulnerable, based on its learned understanding of code syntax and semantics. The classification head consists of a fully connected neural network that outputs a probability distribution over two classes, reflecting the likelihood of a function being secure or containing vulnerabilities.

The process of adapting CodeBERT to SAVE-ME involves several key steps:

1. **Preprocessing Source Code:** Erlang functions are tokenized using an adapted version of CodeBERT’s tokenizer, which we extended by adding Erlang-specific tokens. This enhancement ensures that the tokenizer can better handle Erlang’s unique syntax and constructs, such as atoms, pattern matching, and message-passing primitives. The tokenized output preserves the structural and semantic information of the code, which is critical for identifying complex vulnerability patterns.
2. **Transformer Layers:** The tokenized sequences are passed through CodeBERT’s pre-trained transformer layers, which encode the contextual relationships between tokens. This step captures long-range dependencies and semantic information, enabling the model to understand intricate interactions within the code.
3. **Classification Head:** The encoded output from the final transformer layer is fed into a task-specific fully connected layer, which computes a confidence over two classes: vulnerable and non-vulnerable.
4. **Fine-Tuning on Labeled Data:** SAVE-ME is fine-tuned on an Erlang-specific dataset where each function is annotated with a vulnerability label. During this phase, the model’s weights are adjusted to optimize its predictions for the given task, ensuring that it captures Erlang-specific security patterns effectively.

Training SAVE-ME requires a labeled dataset of Erlang functions, where each function is tagged as either vulnerable or secure. To generate this dataset, we leverage Infer, a static code analysis tool, to analyze various Erlang projects and extract labeled examples of vulnerable and non-vulnerable functions. The use of InfERL [27] provides an initial set of labels, which are then refined with manual inspection and expert feedback to ensure accuracy and reduce false positives.

Function-level granularity is critical for detecting vulnerabilities in Erlang code. Unlike object-oriented languages, vulnerabilities in functional programming often stem from improper handling of data flows, concurrency, or inter-process communication, which are best analyzed within the context of a complete function. SAVE-ME leverages CodeBERT’s ability to capture contextual relationships and applies this understanding to entire functions, enabling it to

SAVE-ME Pipeline Overview

Figure 5: Overview of the SAVE-ME architecture with pipeline

identify subtle patterns indicative of vulnerabilities. For example, SAVE-ME can detect issues where a function mishandles asynchronous message passing, leading to potential security risks that traditional static analysis tools may overlook.

To create the labeled dataset necessary for training SAVE-ME, we leverage InfERL, Meta’s extension of the Infer static analysis tool, which has been specifically designed to analyze Erlang code. InfERL [27] addresses unique challenges in analyzing Erlang’s functional programming aspects, dynamic types, and concurrency model. It is used in WhatsApp’s backend to detect a broad range of issues, such as unmatched case clauses, invalid map operations, and incorrect function calls.

The tool’s architecture integrates a new Erlang frontend with Infer’s Pulse and Topl analyzers, enabling rapid scalability and customization for user-defined checks. By translating Erlang code to Infer’s intermediate language, InfERL performs efficient, compositional analysis with linear scalability relative to function count. This speed and modularity make InfERL highly

suitable for labeling code efficiently, facilitating ML/DL workflows by systematically generating labeled error data across large code bases.

By utilizing InFERL to generate labeled datasets, SAVE-ME ensures its fine-tuning process is grounded in accurate, representative examples of vulnerable and secure Erlang functions. This integration bridges traditional static analysis with modern machine learning techniques, creating a robust pipeline for detecting and addressing security vulnerabilities.

Erlang's concurrency model, which relies heavily on message-passing and lightweight processes, introduces unique security challenges that require specialized handling. Traditional static analysis tools often fall short in addressing these challenges due to their reliance on syntactic rules or limited contextual understanding. SAVE-ME bridges this gap by leveraging CodeBERT's pre-trained knowledge and enhancing it through fine-tuning on Erlang-specific data.

SAVE-ME exemplifies how pretrained models like CodeBERT can be adapted to address domain-specific challenges in code analysis. Beyond vulnerability detection, this framework can be extended to other security-related tasks, such as detecting coding anti-patterns, generating secure code suggestions, or identifying performance bottlenecks in Erlang projects.

By combining the strengths of CodeBERT with the added functionality of a classification head and fine-tuning on Erlang-specific datasets, SAVE-ME represents a significant step forward in enhancing static analysis tools for secure software development.

4.1.3 Integration Into the Static Analysis Module

The part of the Static Code Analysis Module that uses the fine-tuned CodeBERT model to classify Erlang code as vulnerable or not, as explained in the previous section, is called Static Analysis of Vulnerabilities – Machine Learning Enhancements (SAVE-ME).

The input to SAVE-ME is the tokenized code of an Erlang function. The Erlang code is tokenized using a custom tokenizer tailored for Erlang. Based on this input, SAVE-ME classifies the input function as either vulnerable or non-vulnerable. Specifically, the output consists of an indicator – 0 for non-vulnerable, 1 for vulnerable – as well as confidence scores associated with each classification. This output of SAVE-ME will be visible in SSCG.

SAVE-ME can be used in two ways:

- As a stand-alone tool, where, for a given Erlang function, it returns a prediction indicating whether the function is vulnerable, along with corresponding confidence scores.
- As an enhancement to Infer's output, where SAVE-ME provides a confidence level for Infer's predictions.

SAVE-ME outputs the predictions in SARIF format. The output is validated using the SARIF validator available at <https://sarifweb.azurewebsites.net/Validation>. A sample output is shown in the Appendix B.2.

Using the SAVE-ME module is straightforward, as it is encapsulated in its own Docker container. It can be invoked using:

```
sudo docker run \  
-v $(pwd)/Erlang_input_code:/app/SAVE-ME/Input \  
-v $(pwd)/Results:/app/SAVE-ME/Output \  
save-me
```

Currently, the SAVE-ME module requires two arguments:

- `Erlang_input_code`: Path to the directory where the Erlang functions (contained in `.erl` files) are stored.
- `Results`: Path to the directory where the results, as explained earlier, will be written in SARIF.

4.1.4 Enhancements over Existing Solutions

Using SAVE-ME for Erlang vulnerability classification provides enhancements to traditional static analysis tools:

- By fine-tuning SAVE-ME on Erlang source code, we adapt the model to recognize vulnerabilities unique to the language, such as bad record bug.
- CodeBERT’s contextual understanding of code allows SAVE-ME to distinguish between similar patterns that are secure versus those that are vulnerable, which helps to lower the rate of false positives. This reduces the burden on security teams by minimizing unnecessary alerts and focusing on actual vulnerabilities.
- CodeBERT is integrated into Static Code Analysis Module pipeline to automatically classify vulnerabilities in the provided Erlang codebase, as it is shown on the Figure 12, reducing the need for manual review and improving scalability.

4.2 SASTer: Static Application Security Tester

Static Application Security Tester (SASTer) is a modular and extensible tool designed to streamline the process of analyzing source code for security vulnerabilities and coding errors.

SASTer enables the seamless integration and execution of multiple open-source Static Application Security Testing (SAST) analyzers. Its primary aim is to simplify security testing across diverse programming languages by providing a unified interface and standardized output formats.

4.2.1 SASTer-GUI

The SASTer GUI version provides an intuitive and centralized interface for managing and analyzing source code. It enables users to upload code, conduct static code analysis using a plethora of analyzers and visualize results through the dashboard. Key features of SASTer are explained below:

- **Multi-Language Support:** SASTer currently supports static analysis for multiple popular programming languages such as Python [23], JavaScript [50], C [38] and C++ [73]. It leverages static code analyzers like Bandit (Python) [58], Flawfinder (C/C++) [82], Cppcheck (C/C++) [74], ESLint (JavaScript) [22] and Semgrep (Several languages) [68], among others.
- **Standardized Outputs:** To integrate seamlessly with downstream workflows, SASTer adopts the Static Analysis Results Interchange Format (SARIF) for its results.
- **Tool Modularity:** Each supported analyzer operates within its own containerized environment (leveraging Docker [18]), ensuring ensuring portability, consistency and isolation during analysis. Analyzers can be easily updated without impacting the tool's overall functionality.
- **Extensibility:** The analyzer's architecture allows new analyzers to be integrated with minimal effort, using scripts and tool-specific loaders.
- **User-Friendly Interface:** SASTer provides a modern web-based interface, offering features such as user authentication, project management and dashboard views for results.
- **Access control:** User-based access control is enforced to allow multiple users to utilize SASTer while protecting intellectual property.

By consolidating the execution of various SAST analyzers, SASTer reduces the complexity of managing multiple static code analyzers, accelerates the identification of vulnerabilities and promotes better security practices throughout the software development lifecycle.

4.2.1.1 Architecture

The architecture of SASTer is designed to provide a modular, extensible, effective and user-friendly platform for integrating multiple SAST analyzers. It leverages containerization, a centralized web interface and a robust backend to ensure consistency, scalability and ease of use. The core components of the architecture are described below in detail:

- **Web Interface:** The Web Interface serves as the user-facing component of the tool, providing an intuitive and dynamic environment for interaction. It is responsible for presenting data and facilitating user actions, its primary features include:
 - **Dashboard:** Displays analysis results in a user-friendly format.
 - **Project Management Interface:** Enables users to upload, organize and manage their code projects via an intuitive interface.
 - **Authentication Interface:** Provides forms for user registration, login and account management, sending user credentials to the backend for processing.

The Web Interface is limited to presentation and interaction. Authentication, session management are implemented in the Backend.

- **Backend System:** The Backend System manages the core logic and operations of the platform, acting as the processing layer between the Web Interface and the Analysis Modules. Built using Flask [62] and Flask-SQLAlchemy [63], it is responsible for the following:
 - User Authentication and session management: Verifies user credentials, manages secure login/logout workflows and maintains active user sessions.
 - Project Orchestration: Manages project uploads, triggers analysis jobs and coordinates results processing with the analysis modules.
 - Database Management: Stores user credentials, project metadata and tool configurations in a relational database using Flask-SQLAlchemy [63].
 - RESTful API Services: Provides endpoints to facilitate communication between the Web Interface and the backend, ensuring smooth data exchange.
- **Modules:** Each SAST tool or module, as is called inside SASTer, is encapsulated within its own Docker container, ensuring isolation since tools run independently and avoiding conflicts or interference. Moreover, the dockerization ensures consistency since tool environments are standardized and reproducible. Each tool is integrated through a consistent modular structure comprised of the following components:
 - Dockerfile: Defines the containerized environment for the tool, including its dependencies, configurations and execution commands.
 - Loader Script: Initializes and dynamically loads the tool into the system.
 - Analysis Script: Executes static analysis using environment-specific parameters.
 - Result Handler: Retrieves and processes the output, converting it to SARIF if necessary.
- **Result Standardization:** Results are standardized into SARIF, either natively or through custom conversion mechanisms, such as scripts that transform JSON or XML output to SARIF. Most if not all static code analyzers support either JSON or XML output format. This ensures compatibility with external tools and CI/CD pipelines.

The process of analyzing source code with SASTer is designed to be intuitive and efficient. Below, we outline the key steps (workflow) users follow to interact with the platform and conduct their code analysis:

1. **Logging In:** Users begin by logging into SASTer using their credentials. If they don't have an account, they must create one.
2. **Creating a Project:** After logging in, users create a project where their code files will be analyzed.
3. **Uploading Code Files:** Users upload their source code files to the created project through the web-based interface.
4. **Automatic Tool Selection and Execution:** Based on the uploaded file types (e.g., .py, .c, .js), SASTer automatically identifies the appropriate analyzers for the programming languages detected. The system then spawns the necessary Docker containers to execute these tools.

5. **Processing and Standardizing Results:** Once the analysis is complete, SASTer retrieves the results from each tool. If required, custom scripts are used to convert the output into the standardized SARIF format.
6. **Reviewing Results:** The processed results are displayed on the user's dashboard, providing clear insights into identified vulnerabilities and enabling users to address potential issues effectively.

This structured process ensures that users can efficiently analyze their code for vulnerabilities with minimal effort.

4.2.1.2 ML/DL Integration

SASTer plans to incorporate ML and DL techniques to further enhance the accuracy and efficiency of its static analysis processes. These planned advancements aim to reduce false positives, eliminate duplicate results and provide actionable guidance to users for addressing vulnerabilities.

Once implemented, the ML/DL modules will parse analyzer outputs post-processing, identifying redundant findings and suppressing less critical issues to present users with a prioritized and refined list of vulnerabilities. This will ensure that developers can focus on resolving the most significant security concerns efficiently. Additionally, code recommendations will be generated, assisting users in fixing vulnerabilities.

By integrating ML/DL methods into SASTer, the tool will streamline the analysis process and empower developers with precise and actionable insights, marking a significant step forward in static application security testing.

4.2.1.3 Evaluation Results

SASTer has undergone thorough evaluation to ensure its robustness, efficiency and accuracy in performing static application security testing. The tool has been rigorously tested across a diverse range of source code files, encompassing programming languages such as Python, C, C++ and JavaScript. This comprehensive testing process has demonstrated SASTer's ability to seamlessly integrate and execute a variety of static code analyzers, consistently delivering actionable and standardized results.

The evaluation process has confirmed the tool's capability to accurately detect security vulnerabilities, ensuring developers can trust the results provided. Each supported analyzer has been validated in its dockerized environment to guarantee reliable and consistent performance across supported languages. Additionally, SASTer's automated workflows and SARIF standardization have been shown to significantly streamline the analysis process, reducing manual effort and improving the overall efficiency of software security assessments.

To provide a clearer understanding of SASTer's functionality and user experience, the figures below showcase key components of the platform.

Figure 6: SASTer Dashboard

Figure 6 highlights the SASTer dashboard, which provides users with an overview of their projects. This interface includes information about created projects and the status of ongoing or completed analyses.

Figure 7: SASTer Analysis

Figure 7 shows the page users encounter after starting the analysis of their code. Here, users can monitor the execution of selected tools on their uploaded files. This screen provides updates on the status of the analysis, ensuring transparency and allowing users to track the progress of their static code analysis.

Figure 8: SASTer Results

Figure 8 presents the results interface, where users can view identified vulnerabilities after an analysis is completed. This screen organizes results in a structured format, presenting the severity and type of vulnerabilities.

4.2.2 SASTer-CLI

The SASTer CLI tool provides a streamlined and flexible alternative to the GUI version, allowing users to perform static code analysis directly from the terminal. Designed for both automation and efficiency, the CLI tool offers SASTer’s capabilities to users who prefer or require command-line workflows.

The tool supports online and offline modes. The online mode, still under development, will connect in the future to a SASTer live instance, leveraging most of the tools features, such as containerized static analyzers, etc. It simply provides a way to access SASTer’s full capabilities without using the GUI, relying instead on command-line operations for flexibility, automation and integration on existing workflows.

On the other hand, the offline mode, which is currently operational, enables direct integration of static analyzers within a user’s environment, focusing on essential functionality such as running supported tools and generating standardized outputs. The offline mode works locally, without the need to connect to the live service or even go online. The only requirement is that the static code analyzers are already installed on the user’s system.

The offline mode shares many of the core advantages of the SASTer GUI version, such as a modular architecture and the ability to easily incorporate additional analyzers. However, the offline mode is more lightweight by design, omitting some of the advanced features of the GUI version. For instance, while the GUI version includes containerized analyzers for streamlined deployment, the CLI tool’s offline mode relies on direct integration of the analyzers within the

user's environment, offering a more manual but flexible approach.

4.2.2.1 Architecture

This section describes the architecture of the offline mode of the SASTer CLI tool, as it is the currently operational mode. It details the structural design and components that enable the tool to integrate static analyzers, execute scans and produce standardized outputs locally within a user's environment.

The architecture of the SASTer CLI tool's offline mode is designed to provide a modular and efficient framework for static code analysis. The core components that interact to perform static code analysis are described below:

- **Command Processing:** The CLI acts as the primary interface, interpreting user commands to initiate actions, such as scanning code files. SASTer-CLI uses “argparse” to handle commands (e.g., scan, version), a Python library used for parsing command-line arguments, thus ensuring appropriate workflows are executed.
- **Configuration Management:** The CLI tool manages runtime settings through a structured configuration mechanism. These configurations define parameters such as logging levels and output preferences. The configuration is loaded via the “config.ini” file (and falls back to defaults if the file is absent).
- **Logging Mechanism:** The CLI tool includes a robust logging mechanism to provide detailed feedback on execution processes. It supports multiple severity levels (e.g., informational, warning, error) to ensure users are well-informed about operations and any potential issues. This is handled by the “logger” module.
- **Static Analyzer Integration:** The SASTer CLI tool's offline mode uses a modular approach for integrating static code analyzers. Static analyzers are integrated as independent modules, each responsible for its own initialization and execution. While not formalized under a strict interface, this design ensures flexibility in supporting different analyzers. The approach simplifies the addition of new analyzers and provides support for diverse programming languages.
- **Execution Engine:** The execution engine coordinates the scanning process by invoking analyzers on the source code provided by the user. It ensures that analyzers are executed efficiently and their outputs are collected for further processing.
- **Result Generation:** Results can be generated in various formats, including SARIF. For analyzers that do not natively support SARIF, the offline mode employs parsers to convert JSON or XML outputs that many analyzers support into SARIF, maintaining uniformity.

4.2.2.2 Evaluation Results

The evaluation of the SASTer CLI tool focused on its offline mode, assessing its effectiveness in executing static code analysis. The tool was tested across diverse codebases using its currently

supported analyzers. At this moment, the offline mode supports Flawfinder, Bandit, Semgrep, Bearer, Horusec and Cppcheck, thus it can scan python and C/C++ codebases.

The lightweight design and command-line-driven workflow proved effective for integration into automated environments, such as CI/CD pipelines, with minimal setup. To run a scan using the offline mode, the command is:

```
python3 saster-cli.py scan --offline \  
-m Bandit,Flawfinder,Semgrep,Horusec \  
-o results.sarif project --verbose
```



```
(kali@kali)~[~/Downloads/tool-saster-cli]  
$ python3 saster-cli.py scan --offline -m Horusec,Bandit,Flawfinder,Semgrep -o results.sarif project --verbose  
[INFO] Module Bandit initialised successfully.  
[INFO] Module Semgrep initialised successfully.  
[INFO] Module Flawfinder initialised successfully.  
[INFO] Module Horusec initialised successfully.  
[INFO] Bandit version detected: bandit 1.7.10  
python version = 3.12.6 (main, Sep 7 2024, 14:20:15) [GCC 14.2.0]  
[INFO] Module Bandit loaded successfully.  
[INFO] Semgrep version detected: 1.97.0  
[INFO] Module Semgrep loaded successfully.  
[INFO] Flawfinder version detected: 2.0.19  
[INFO] Module Flawfinder loaded successfully.  
[INFO] Horusec version detected: Version: v2.8.0  
Git commit: df32c1ce03d2de748cecb76cff383f2851e198c3  
Built: Wed Jun 08 13:57:08 2022  
Distribution: normal  
[INFO] Module Horusec loaded successfully.  
[main] INFO profile include tests: None  
[main] INFO profile exclude tests: None  
[main] INFO cli include tests: None  
[main] INFO cli exclude tests: None  
[main] INFO running on Python 3.12.6  
[INFO] Bandit analysis completed successfully.  
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_bandit.sarif.  
[INFO] Flawfinder analysis completed successfully.  
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_flawfinder.sarif.  
[INFO] Horusec analysis completed successfully.  
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_horusec.sarif.  
[INFO] Semgrep analysis completed successfully.  
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_semgrep.sarif.  
[INFO] All module scans completed.
```

Figure 9: SASTER CLI

Figure 9 shows the SASTER CLI tool performing a scan in offline mode, utilizing multiple static analyzers, including Horusec, Bandit, Flawfinder and Semgrep. The respective versions and configurations of the analyzers are logged for transparency. The tool processes the provided project directory and outputs SARIF-compliant results for each analyzer. One of the SARIF outputs can be found in B.3. The verbose mode enhances visibility into the execution process, confirming successful initialization, execution and result generation for all modules.

4.2.3 Integration Into the Static Analysis Module

The SASTER CLI tool, along with its dependencies and analyzers, is packaged in a lightweight container image based on a Debian slim distribution, ensuring minimal overhead while maintaining functionality.

The Docker-based integration automates the setup of the required environment, including the installation of static analyzers such as Flawfinder, Semgrep, Bandit, Horusec, Bearer and Cp-pcheck. These analyzers are installed alongside the code of the SASTer CLI, enabling the execution of comprehensive static code analysis within the container.

To integrate the tool, the source code is included as part of the Docker build process and placed in a dedicated directory within the container.

This containerized approach allows the SASTer CLI to be integrated into the Static Code Analysis Module with minimal configuration. The SASTer container can be invoked using the following command:

```
sudo docker run \  
-v $(pwd)/project:/saster-tool/project \  
-v $(pwd)/results:/saster-tool/results \  
saster-cli:latest \  
saster-cli scan --offline -m Bandit,Flawfinder,Semgrep,Horusec -o \  
/saster-tool/results/results.sarif --verbose
```

This command mounts the project folder in the current directory into the container's `/saster-tool/project` directory, which contains the source code to be analyzed. Similarly, it mounts the results folder into the container's `/saster-tool/results` directory, where the output files will be saved. The “saster-cli:latest” image specifies the Docker image to run. Inside the container, the “saster-cli” command is executed in offline mode, using the analyzers Bandit, Flawfinder, Semgrep and Horusec.

4.2.4 Enhancements over Existing Solutions

SASTer represents a significant advancement over traditional static code analysis solutions by addressing their limitations and introducing innovative features designed to enhance usability, accuracy and extensibility.

One of the primary innovations of SASTer is its modular architecture, both for the GUI and CLI version which allows seamless integration of multiple analyzers. The architecture simplifies the incorporation of more analyzers while also making updates to existing ones easy.

Another key detail is the adoption of SARIF for output standardization. By converting the diverse outputs of integrated tools into SARIF, SASTer ensures that results are presented in a consistent and actionable format, making it easier for developers to interpret findings and integrate them into CI/CD pipelines. This innovation addresses a common problem in traditional solutions, where inconsistent result formats hinder automation and scalability.

Moreover, planned enhancements, such as the integration of ML/DL for post-processing results, aim to reduce false positives, eliminate duplicate findings and provide recommendations to users. These upcoming features position SASTer as a forward-looking tool designed to adapt to evolving security challenges.

Additionally, SASTer simplifies the developer experience by offering a web-based interface for centralized management and a CLI tool for local execution. This dual approach ensures that SASTer is accessible to a wide range of users, from individual developers to enterprise teams, while maintaining flexibility and control.

By combining modularity, standardization, security and extensibility, SASTer sets a new standard for static code analysis solutions. Its ability to address the limitations of traditional tools while incorporating cutting-edge technologies makes it a transformative platform for software security.

4.2.5 Limitations and Future Enhancements

SASTer, while offering a modular and extensible way for integrating multiple SAST analyzers, has certain limitations that will be addressed in future iterations. One limitation is its current reliance on existing static analyzers, which means the tool's performance is inherently dependent on the capabilities of the integrated analyzers. As a result, SASTer at this moment cannot directly address the limitations of these tools, such as their false positive rates or inability to detect certain advanced vulnerabilities.

Additionally, SASTer doesn't currently support scanning binary code which is often used. The absence of advanced ML/DL modules post-processing for tool outputs is another area that limits SASTer's ability to provide deeper insights, such as vulnerability prioritization and intelligent recommendations.

Planned future enhancements for SASTer include the integration of ML/DL capabilities to reduce false positives, detect duplicate results and provide actionable recommendations. Moreover, future iterations of SASTer could provide support for binary code analysis. These improvements will ensure that SASTer continues to evolve as a robust and versatile tool for secure software development.

4.3 Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE)

The Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE) in RESCALE is designed to address critical gaps in static code analysis by leveraging symbolic execution. Unlike traditional static analyzers, which rely on syntactic and semantic analysis, the IVEE introduces a another layer to assess code comprehensively. This tool focuses primarily on symbolic execution to detect vulnerabilities in compiled binary files. The symbolic execution capabilities of the IVEE systematically explore all feasible execution paths using symbolic inputs, ensuring that property violations (e.g., assertion failures) are detected across various execution paths.

The IVEE achieves this by combining symbolic execution with static analysis features like Control Flow Graph (CFG) generation. This approach allows for an exhaustive assessment of a software component's behavior under diverse scenarios, helping to identify vulnerabilities that might be missed by conventional tools. By using symbolic execution, the IVEE provides concrete counterexamples when properties are violated, helping developers pinpoint the exact inputs that lead to failure.

4.3.1 Core Components and Functionality

The backbone of the IVEE is the Angr framework [21], which enables the symbolic execution of binary executables. Symbolic execution allows the IVEE to explore multiple execution paths in a program by treating inputs as symbolic variables instead of concrete values. This approach allows the tool to detect vulnerabilities that depend on specific execution paths, such as buffer overflows, use-after-free, integer overflows and other critical security issues. Angr’s symbolic execution engine handles path exploration, constraint solving and counterexample generation to identify flaws in the software’s behavior. The core symbolic execution component in the IVEE is based on “`angr.simulation_manager`”, a Python class in the Angr framework responsible for orchestrating the management of execution paths. It provides functions for branching, pruning and evaluating constraints to identify property violations such as assertion failures or security checks.

The IVEE is able to scan several types of compiled binary files, such as Executable and Linkable Format (ELF) for Linux and Portable Executable (PE) for Windows. These formats are ideal for symbolic analysis because they contain the binary code that the symbolic execution engine needs to analyze. By focusing on compiled binary code, the IVEE eliminates the need for handling source code, making it an efficient tool for post-compilation vulnerability detection.

One of the IVEE’s key features is the ability to automatically explore feasible execution paths using Angr’s “ExplorationTechnique”. This process involves searching for paths that may lead to vulnerabilities, focusing on areas of the code where such issues are most likely to arise. The IVEE will embed specific properties as assertions or constraints and use symbolic execution to verify whether these properties hold true across different execution paths. If a property violation occurs, Angr’s solver will provide counterexamples, which are concrete inputs that trigger the violation, helping developers understand the conditions under which vulnerabilities can be exploited.

To better understand the structure of binaries, the IVEE will also generate different CFGs using “`angr.analyses.CFGFast`”. These graphs visualize the flow of execution through the binary, helping the analysis engine identify key areas of interest, such as loops, conditionals and function calls. By visualizing the control flow, the IVEE can prioritize regions of code that are more likely to contain vulnerabilities, allowing it to focus the symbolic execution on critical sections.

The IVEE will use symbolic execution to detect property violations, such as assertion failures, buffer overflows and other security vulnerabilities. Angr’s symbolic execution engine enables the detection of these violations by exploring multiple execution paths and generating path constraints. When a violation is detected, IVEE will use Angr’s solver to generate concrete inputs, known as counterexamples, which can reproduce the failure. These counterexamples provide valuable insight into the input conditions that cause the vulnerability, enabling developers to patch or mitigate the issue.

Initially, the IVEE will focus on supporting C/C++ and Python-generated binaries. This decision is driven by the prevalence of these languages in system-level programming and the fact that many vulnerabilities (e.g., buffer overflows, uninitialized variables) are most commonly found in C/C++ applications. The IVEE will analyze these compiled binaries to detect vulnerabilities that are specific to these languages.

4.3.2 Considerations and Enhancements

While Angr provides a robust symbolic execution engine, there are a few considerations and potential enhancements for the IVEE's initial version:

- **Path Explosion:** As with any symbolic execution tool, the IVEE may encounter the path explosion problem when analyzing large or complex codebases. This occurs when the number of feasible execution paths grows exponentially, leading to significant computational overhead. To mitigate this, the IVEE will incorporate various path exploration optimizations, such as path pruning and state merging, to reduce the number of paths explored and improve performance.
- **Dynamic Features and Limitations:** Although Angr is highly effective for static code analysis, it might miss certain vulnerabilities that rely on runtime behavior. To address this, the IVEE will eventually integrate dynamic analysis techniques, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis that captures runtime behavior and dynamic vulnerabilities.
- **Integration with Traditional Static Code Analyzers:** To further enhance its capabilities, the IVEE could integrate with other static analysis tools like Bandit or Semgrep for static analysis, helping to prioritize potentially vulnerable code regions before running symbolic execution.
- **Machine Learning (ML) Enhancements:** Incorporating ML models could improve the prioritization of execution paths based on historical vulnerability data, making the tool more adaptive and intelligent.

The IVEE represents a powerful tool for static code analysis, focusing on symbolic execution to identify vulnerabilities in binary code. By leveraging Angr's symbolic execution capabilities, the IVEE offers automated, high-coverage analysis of binaries, including support for C/C++ and Python executables. With its ability to detect property violations and provide counterexamples, the IVEE plays a critical role in enhancing software security. Future improvements, will further strengthen the IVEE's ability to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities across a wide range of software applications.

4.4 Efforts Related to RefactorERL

RefactorERL [8] is an advanced tool designed for static analysis and refactoring of Erlang code, helping developers ensure code quality and maintainability through automated analysis techniques. With capabilities to analyze code structure, detect potential issues, and suggest improvements, RefactorERL serves as a critical asset for projects relying on the Erlang ecosystem to refine their applications.

RefactorERL's potential contribution to RESCALE, particularly in the integration of ML/DL techniques for Erlang-specific static analysis, is significant. However, an assessment led by PST revealed several obstacles related to RefactorERL's current state as a software project. Currently hosted in a private repository at ELTE University, RefactorERL lacks the visibility and collaborative framework offered by platforms like GitHub, which has introduced challenges in both maintenance and community engagement. Notable issues include:

- **Internal Development Barriers:** Numerous unmerged internal features and reliability issues impact RefactorERL's static analysis functions.
- **Outdated Compatibility:** The tool does not fully support recent versions of Erlang, limiting its usability in contemporary projects.
- **Proprietary Components:** Certain advanced features remain proprietary, owned by an external company, and are not included in the open-source version.

To address these challenges, PST has taken several proactive steps:

- **Repository Migration to GitHub:** Recognizing the importance of making RefactorERL more accessible, PST initiated a migration to GitHub, which ELTE University is managing. To support this, PST has offered direct assistance in the migration process and in resolving reliability issues that hamper the tool's performance.
- **Negotiations to Expand Open-Source Components:** PST is in contact with the company owning the proprietary components to explore options for making these available as open-source.

The migration to GitHub aligns with the Erlang community's expectations. This community is highly collaborative, with members actively contributing improvements, bug reports, and pull requests. Hosting RefactorERL on GitHub will allow the community to engage with the tool directly, an opportunity that has been limited in its current private repository setup. Without GitHub's open framework, projects often face negative reception due to limited community involvement, which is critical in the Erlang ecosystem.

At this stage, it is not advisable to add complex ML/DL features to RefactorERL until these foundational issues are addressed. Given RefactorERL's robust capabilities and its unique role in the Erlang community, PST remains committed to ensuring it becomes an accessible and well-supported resource.

5 Formal Verification

Formal verification is a mathematical approach to proving the correctness of systems, particularly in software and hardware design, ensuring they function as intended under all possible conditions. There are several flavors, including model checking, which explores all possible states of a system, and theorem proving, which relies on mathematical logic and requires extensive user input. Applications of formal verification span critical fields like aerospace, automotive, and medical devices, where system failures can be catastrophic. However, limitations include high complexity, scalability issues, and the need for expert knowledge, which can make it impractical for large, complex systems. The RESCALE project is dedicated to advancing and refining formal verification methods specifically for the Erlang programming language.

5.1 DetectEr

Erlang is a functional, concurrent programming language built around the Actor model [30], where independent processes communicate via asynchronous message passing. While this design makes Erlang ideal for building distributed and fault-tolerant systems, the complexities of its concurrency model make formal verification particularly difficult:

1. **Concurrency and Message Passing:** Erlang's non-deterministic message passing and concurrency imply race conditions and a complex state space, making verification challenging.
2. **Dynamic Typing and Code Behavior:** Erlang's dynamic typing and hot code swapping (a way of updating code at runtime without downtime) complicate static analysis and predicting system behavior over time, which hinders formal verification.
3. **Side Effects and Process Behavior:** Erlang's processes often produce side effects from interactions with external systems, making them difficult to model and verify accurately.

Formal verification in Erlang often requires making assumptions about the analyzed code, such as simplifying the behavior of processes or restricting concurrency. While these assumptions make verification feasible, they are usually too strict for real-world applications, limiting the practicality and completeness of the verification results.

DetectEr [4], a runtime verification tool for Erlang, strikes a useful compromise by monitoring system behavior at runtime to detect concurrency errors like race conditions and message passing issues. Instead of requiring strict assumptions, DetectEr allows systems to run in real-world conditions while still checking for violations of safety properties, offering a more practical approach to improving reliability without the overhead of exhaustive formal verification. DetectEr operates on execution traces of selective parts of a system, collecting events either through inline code instrumentation, external tracing, or offline analysis. These traces represent the program's runtime behavior, which DetectEr then analyzes against properties specified in safe Hennessy–Milner Logic (sHML) [11] logic.

In the scope of RESCALE those safety properties (a formal model) will be developed for specific Erlang applications under scrutiny. It should be emphasized that these safety properties are

always specific for a certain application as they describe an individual program behavior. While DetectEr itself is a dynamic analysis tool the development of the safety properties is a subject of static code analysis and therefore covered in T3.1 related activities. The RESCALE project and its pilot partner PST will be the first industry connected user of DetectEr and therefore serve towards a first real-world application.

5.1.1 Hennessy–Milner Logic and Safety Properties

Hennessy–Milner Logic (HML) [29] is a logic designed for describing the behaviors of concurrent systems. It uses modal operators to express the possibility and necessity of state transitions within a system. HML allows reasoning about what actions are possible or required in specific states. There is a variant called “Hennessy-Milner Logic with recursion” [31] (modal μ -calculus [39]), which extends HML by introducing recursion, enabling more complex properties to be specified. sHML is a syntactic subset of this logic, used to specify so-called safety properties, and is utilized by DetectEr. While DetectEr works on traces of executed programs, the reasoning it performs is about properties of the programs themselves, and not about the traces. However, there is a flavor of DetectEr that can reason directly about traces, which is out of scope of this document.

In HML, recursion is used through the concept of fixpoints, allowing properties to be defined in a self-referential way. This is crucial for expressing behaviors that involve looping or ongoing conditions in concurrent systems. Fixpoints come in two forms: the least fixpoint for properties that must eventually hold, and the maximal fixpoint for properties that must hold indefinitely over the execution of a system. sHML only focuses on maximal fixpoints which are then used to describe “safety properties”, ensuring that something bad never happens during the system’s execution. By using these fixpoints, sHML enables the expression of ongoing constraints that must remain valid across all reachable states.

With this background, sHML formulae are generated from the following grammar:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi \in \text{sHML} ::= & \text{ff} \mid \text{tt} & (1) \\ & \mid X & (2) \\ & \mid \max(X.\phi) & (3) \\ & \mid \text{and}([\alpha_1]\phi_1, \dots, [\alpha_n]\phi_n) & (4) \end{aligned}$$

1. The formulae ff and tt represent falsity and truth, respectively.
2. X is a logical variable.
3. The maximal fixpoint construct, $\max(X.\phi)$, defines recursion through the variable X and binds its free occurrences in the sub-formula ϕ .
4. $\text{and}([\alpha_1]\phi_1, \dots, [\alpha_n]\phi_n)$ is a conjunction of sub-formulae ϕ_i , each guarded by the universal modal operator $[\alpha_i]$ (also called *necessity*).

To handle reasoning over program event data, the modal operator uses symbolic actions α of the form “ P when C ”, where P is an event pattern and C is a decidable Boolean constraint. Patterns represent events that occur in the program under analysis and contain data variables

that get instantiated with values observed at runtime. These variables bind the free variables in constraints C , extending their scope to the continuation formula ϕ . With DetectEr event patterns are formulated using Erlang pattern matching syntax and they support the expression of message passing and process behavior (like spawning a new process from an existing one).

A program (or state) satisfies the formula $[P \text{ when } C]\phi$ if it exhibits an event matching P , meets the constraint C , and the subsequent program behavior satisfies ϕ . If the constraint C is true, the expression “when C ” can be omitted for simplicity.

The following describes a very simple example of a sHML formula involving inter-process communication and pattern matching:

$$\text{and}([\text{Pid1:Pid2} ! [\text{Number}] \text{ when } \text{Number} \leq 0])\text{ff}$$

The event pattern “Pid1:Pid2 ! [Number]” describes two processes, identified by their IDs, where Pid1 sends a message “[Number]” (an Erlang list with exactly one element) to Pid2. Note that the continuation formula here is ff (falsity), which cannot be satisfied. Hence the overall formula can only be satisfied when the event pattern *under* the condition “Number \leq 0” is not exhibited by the program under scrutiny.

In the context of DetectEr, sHML formulas must be embedded into a structure which allows to identify code signatures to monitor:

$$\text{with hello:world() monitor } \phi$$

Here, the safety property ϕ is applied to traces originating from the module “hello” and function “world” (Erlang code is organized in modules containing functions). Hence only a specific part of a program is actually monitored using specified safety properties. The above statement is valid Erlang code and can be compiled and applied to traces using DetectEr. This completes the creation of a formal model for safety properties.

5.1.2 Application to a Software Update Mechanism

The project partner PST uses an A/B software update mechanism to update Internet of Things (IoT) devices over-the-air in various projects. A/B software updates are a method used to update software on a device while minimizing downtime and reducing the risk of a failed update. The concept involves having two partitions, A and B, each capable of holding a complete copy of the system software. It works the following way:

- **Dual Partitions:** The device maintains two separate partitions: A and B. One partition is active (running the current software), while the other is inactive.
- **Background Update:** The software update is applied to the inactive partition in the background while the device continues to operate normally using the active partition.
- **Seamless Switch:** Once the update is complete, the device simply switches to boot from the newly updated partition during the next restart. If the update fails, it can revert to the old partition, ensuring that the device remains functional.

A/B updates are popular in smartphones, IoT devices, and other embedded systems that require consistent uptime and safety during software upgrades. For the maintenance of IoT devices from PST this update mechanism is the single most important piece of software affecting more than 20000 high value devices in the field.

There are certain details in the way A/B updates are executed, especially when unstable networks (like mobile networks) or cryptographic hardware (for e.g., secure boot and encryption) are involved. So it can be necessary to only download update data that was not already downloaded, using e.g., hashed blocks of partition data, or manage additional cryptographic material to make the updated partition usable. Further update packages can be signed and hence validated during the download.

The following is a list of high level “safety properties” which are desirable to be verified with DetectEr:

- **Integrity of the Update Process:** Ensure that the update is applied only to the inactive partition without corruption, using cryptographic checks for validation.
- **Rollback Mechanism:** Verify that the device can revert to the previous partition if the update fails, keeping the device operational.
- **Network Interruption Handling:** Confirm that the update process can handle network interruptions, resuming correctly without data loss or corruption.
- **Authentication of Update Source:** Ensure that updates are only accepted from authorized sources, using cryptographic methods to verify the authenticity of the update package.

These properties are not yet translated into a formal model but serve as a starting point for future work.

6 SSCG Design and Generation

The Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG) is supposed to capture the results of the previously elaborated static code analyzers and formal verification mechanisms together with appropriate metadata to make it machine processable. After generating the SSCG it is sent to the RESCALE Management Module by the Producer where it is made available for Consumers for the second step of the RESCALE workflow, the dynamic testing.

6.1 Requirements

As partially addressed in D4.1, the SSCG should enable the reader not only to observe test results but also to inform about the overall context of the test procedure and implications of test results, while ensuring that it deserves being trustworthy. Further, the tester is likely executing tests with respect to a set of predefined procedures and goals as part of an (organization-specific) standard. Additionally, the TBOM (as explained in D4.1) mandates that the SSCG must include at least a unique identifier and a timestamp for traceability purposes. More critically, the test findings must encompass vulnerabilities and weaknesses in a processable manner, as they are further exposed and traced through the TBOM.

The following list outlines the high-level requirements and motivations for the SSCG in light of these observations:

1. **Traceability:** The SSCG needs to contain a unique identifier and the time of its generation.
2. **Performed Tests:** The SSCG must include a comprehensive account of all static code analysis tests performed by the Producer on the component.
3. **Test Results:** It must clearly indicate whether vulnerabilities and weaknesses were identified, specifying the nature and severity of any detected issues, in a processable manner.
4. **Asset Version:** The SSCG must capture the precise version of the evaluated software component, ensuring traceability within the supply chain.
5. **Producer's ID:** The identity of the Producer (the entity responsible for conducting the evaluation) must be included for accountability and verification purposes.
6. **Environment Data:** The report should contain metadata about the testing environment, such as system configurations or used hardware, to contextualize and support reproducibility of the results.
7. **Configuration Information:** Any specific configurations applied during the static analysis should be detailed to ensure transparency.
8. **Compliance Standards:** The SSCG should list the security and software quality standards and guidelines that the Producer is targeting for compliance.

9. **Comparability:** The SSCG should be structured in a way that allows for easy comparison with other SSCGs, enabling stakeholders to evaluate different components or systems side by side based on the tests performed, vulnerabilities identified, and compliance with standards.
10. **Authenticity and Integrity:** The SSCG must include mechanisms to ensure the authenticity and integrity of the test reports and its metadata.

It should be emphasized here that the SSCG contains a multitude of test reports, each generated by different tools with possibly different configurations, environments and requirements towards ensuring their authenticity and integrity. Hence each single test report will also contain such a specific set of descriptions. The above list also touches related topics which are elaborated on in the following.

6.1.1 Test Reporting Format

Static analysis tools are effectively, as of today, not guided by an official standard regarding their output format. This means in practice that every tool follows a different output format ranging from plain shell output of newline separated findings to complex folder structures including Extensible Markup Language (XML) or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) reports following different schemas. To tackle this problem of having comparable and interoperable outputs of static analysis tools the Static Analysis Results Interchange Format (SARIF) [67] was developed as an OASIS approved (JSON-based) industry standard without any significant competition. Within RESCALE it is desirable to honor this format when possible.

6.1.2 Reproducible Testing

Since static testing might result in uncovering security findings it is desirable to repeat the testing effort after fixing an issue, or at least provide transparency to other parties to enable them to repeat the test. The latter requirement is in particular important for open source projects where this degree of transparency is not only appreciated but for widely used software projects in the light of the recent XZ Utils backdoor (CVE-2024-3094 [15]) also expected. RESCALE test definitions/descriptions should therefore be sufficiently rich in details to allow different parties to evaluate the tests themselves. Here it appears to be desirable to use a definition language that allows the automation of testing efforts including the hardware and operating system setup. There exist different automation technologies like Ansible [61] and Puppet [57] which allow the description of workflows such that a test can be defined in a machine processable manner. RESCALE will allow a wide range of test definitions starting from plain human readable text to comprehensive machine readable definitions of setups and workflows.

6.1.3 Classification of Artifacts

Further, the SSCG could be able to contain information to classify the state of the respective software artifact according to a defined compliance requirement or standard. This allows a producer to elaborate further on his motivations and testing effort. Such a requirement could

be “The maximum CVSS score of a vulnerability of the tested artifact is not higher than 2” or more technology related like “The static analysis tool RefactorErl was not able to identify any issues which could potentially halt the Erlang Virtual Machine and therefore stop the program execution”. Such requirements can hence be very generic or really technology dependent but also be totally different between organizations that want to ensure to only deploy viable software artifacts.

6.1.4 Classification of Vulnerabilities and Weaknesses

To make static analysis results actionable, they must be categorized using standardized systems that ensure consistent interpretation and processing. Two key frameworks widely adopted for this purpose are **Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)** [77] and **Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)** [78], both maintained by MITRE and commonly integrated into static analysis tools.

CVE provides unique identifiers for publicly disclosed vulnerabilities, allowing organizations to track specific issues consistently. Each CVE entry includes a description of the vulnerability and its potential impact, making it easier to prioritize responses. Static analysis tools often map their findings to CVE entries, enabling organizations to align with global standards and track vulnerabilities across systems. CVE integration allows for streamlined communication and remediation by linking vulnerabilities to well-documented references in databases like the NVD [51].

CWE categorizes common software and hardware weaknesses that could lead to vulnerabilities. While CVE identifies specific vulnerabilities, CWE focuses on the underlying coding flaws (e.g., buffer overflows, improper input validation) that allow these vulnerabilities to exist. Static analysis tools regularly use CWE categories to classify findings, providing deeper insight into the root causes of weaknesses.

It must be emphasized here that a processable classification of findings is necessary to enable an automated TBOM lifecycle, specifically an automated generation of its vulnerability document.

6.2 Initial Design

As outlined in D4.1, CycloneDX (CDX) is a suitable BOM standard in the scope of RESCALE. CDX follows an abstract high-level specification encompassing a variety of metadata, dependencies of the artifact and even workflows that affect its processing like its compilation. While it was initially designed as a relatively simple BOM standard for software artifacts to capture vulnerabilities, it has grown to cover complex use cases involving whole service architectures, hardware components and environment descriptions. One of the most recent updates (in CycloneDX 1.6 [12]) is the addition of attestations which enables CDX to even incorporate testing data with respect to a test target. This addition is crucial since the output of the static code analysis module needs to be part of the SSCG, together with a definition of the actual test and other elements that were mentioned in section 6.1.

An initial specification of the SSCG using CDX serves two key purposes. First, it provides a usable specification for the Minimum Viable Product (MVP), ensuring the project starts with

something functional and testable. CDX offers a well-supported structure, making it an ideal starting point for this integration. Second, this approach allows for practical learning and improvement. By starting with a partially implemented SSCG in CDX, the project can gain insights from real-world use, informing necessary adjustments and refinements as development progresses. While this initial implementation focuses on CDX, transitioning to a neutral format for SSCG specification is under consideration for later stages, as well as adjustments to the CDX standard based on the project's experience.

Figure 10 illustrates the conceptual structure of the SSCG's initial design, as it can be defined using CDX. The SSCG has a core part which contains the all relevant meta data, configuration and tool invocation details with respect to e.g. the static code analysis module, and of course the test output itself. This core part is meant to be the usual output of the static code analysis module. Further, CDX offers the possibility to extend this core part with rather producer specific content in case the he has a set of requirements on the software he wants to verify and also wants to capture the compliance with these requirements in the SSCG as explained in section 6.1.3.

Figure 10: SSCG Concept

Appendix A contains an SSCG example in CDX format, following the structure laid out in figure 10. While a large chunk of the content is self-explanatory there are some parts, especially the “declarations” and “definitions” fields, which need further explanation. As illustrated by figure 11 the “definitions” field contains a list of standards which again allow the definition of a list of “requirements”. These requirements can be used to express software qualities and

the testing effort that needs to be covered in the static analysis testing. Further, the RESCALE workflow can be elaborated here as a principal guideline for processing the software artifact. The example in appendix A includes fictional examples of those standards and requirements to showcase this approach. Please note again, that those definitions are optional as they are part of the extended SSCG.

Figure 11: CycloneDX Attestations Overview

The “declarations” field then contains the actual evidence to support compliance or mismatches with the standards and their requirements. This is done using the definition of “claims” which function as a hypothesis towards a requirement. Such a claim can express that a requirement was violated to a certain degree or on the other side that a requirement is fulfilled. Each claim is carried by “evidence” which is a piece of data to support the hypothesis (e.g., the claim). Note that the SSCG makes heavy use of so called CDX “bom-ref” elements to refer to objects defined in other places; for example, a claim uses the bom-ref of a piece of evidence to refer to the evidence itself. It is possible to attach arbitrary text as evidence here, together with its format identifier such that e.g. JSON can be attached and consumed in a programmatic way. In the scope of the SSCG, the evidence contains test report data, i.e. output from static code analyzers. An example of a claim could be “Memory vulnerabilities related to CVE-2021-44228 were found” (which violates a requirement) while the evidence shows the respective output of a single or even multiple static analyzer tools. In case no standards and requirements are defined, a claim could simply be that a specific static code analyzer found issues, with the respective test output as evidence. Given a sufficiently elaborated standards and requirements catalog (which is out of scope of this document), it is conceivable that e.g., a standard identifier is given to the static code analysis module (as a configuration option) which then executes tests against its set of requirements.

Further, CDX actually allows the above approach of capturing and interpreting test data for multiple test targets at once. The SSCG is specific for a single software artifact and hence the list of test targets will always contain exactly one element. On top of that, CDX allows to add various metadata like information about the “assessor” (the RESCALE Producer sub-entity, that executes actual tests) and even environment and configuration information to a high degree. Also the involved tooling (“tools”) like containers and the SSCG Generator itself can be specified, including invocation information (again, see appendix A).

It should also be mentioned that CDX supports signatures using JSON Signature Format (JSF). This way basically every part of the SSCG document, specifically the attestations related fields, can be signed by the Producer entity using a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI).

6.3 Unification of Test Reports

Unifying the output from multiple static code analysis tools is essential for improving efficiency and simplifying the management of analysis results. One effective approach is to adopt standardized formats, such as SARIF (see also section 6.1.1). SARIF provides a common structure for the output of different tools, ensuring consistency and making it easier to integrate into automated processes like CI/CD pipelines. This standardization reduces complexity by presenting all results in a **uniform format**.

Another approach is to use consolidation frameworks like SonarQube [72] or DefectDojo [16], which are designed to merge and present reports from various static analysis tools in a single, centralized dashboard. By normalizing the data from different sources, these platforms help eliminate duplication and provide a clear, comprehensive overview of all detected issues. This **centralized view** enables teams to prioritize and track vulnerabilities or code issues more effectively.

In the specific context of the RESCALE static code analysis module it could be valuable to build custom **aggregators** to unify outputs from different tools. Custom solutions can parse the outputs of various analysis tools, converting them into a common format fit for further local processing. This would effectively mean that test reports in the SSCG, despite being able to contain detailed reports of single tools, could also be aggregated in a way that the overall sum of executed tests appears as the test result of the static code analysis module in a unified and value added way.

Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) methods can play a transformative role in enhancing custom aggregators for static code analysis by intelligently processing and interpreting large volumes of data generated by multiple tools. Traditional aggregators focus on collecting and normalizing outputs, but with ML/DL integration, aggregators can go beyond simple data merging. ML/DL models could analyze the relationships between different code modules and respective findings and evaluate them in a way that static analysis tools individually might not be capable of.

Figure 12 depicts a possible workflow of aggregation in combination with ML/DL methods. Multiple static code analyzers generate output from a single software project, then their output undergoes tooling specific pre-processing and finally the findings of the specific tools are mapped to code locations in a unified way. This allows an aggregation of finding on a per code location basis such that further processing can be applied to each code location. This code location specific aggregation could be done using ML/DL methods which technically transforms a matrix of tool specific results into a vector of code location specific interpreted findings.

There is also another more subtle element to the usage of ML/DL methods in figure 12. The final vector of interpreted findings and their locations need to be mapped back to the source code in a meaningful and actionable way. Here ML/DL might again become useful, especially since different findings on different code locations can be dependent. Hence a single finding might

Figure 12: Unification of Analyzer Reports with an Example Set of Analyzers

be related to multiple code locations and can be accompanied by suitable meta information.

While WP3 focuses rather on analyzers in the context of ML/DL methods, it is under consideration to develop the idea of such an aggregation mechanism further.

6.4 SARIF

The Static Analysis Results Interchange Format (SARIF) [67] is an open standard designed to unify the output of static analysis tools, facilitating the integration of diverse tools into cohesive development workflows. Standardized by OASIS [52], SARIF addresses the challenges posed by the varied and often incompatible output formats of static analysis tools, which can hinder effective integration and analysis.

SARIF plays a crucial role in RESCALE by enabling a consistent and interoperable way to report static analysis results across multiple tools in the ‘evidence’ section of a SSCG (see section 6.2 and figure 10). This ensures a streamlined process for aggregating, analyzing, and sharing vulnerability reports within the project.

6.4.1 Overview

SARIF employs a JSON-based schema to represent static analysis results, ensuring both human readability and machine processability. This design choice enhances interoperability among tools and platforms, enabling developers to aggregate and analyze results from multiple sources efficiently. In RESCALE, this is particularly valuable for unifying outputs from a diverse set of static analysis tools.

A key advantage of SARIF is its ability to encapsulate comprehensive information about anal-

ysis results, including details about the tool that generated the results, the rules applied during analysis and the specific locations in the code where issues were detected. This rich metadata supports advanced scenarios such as automated bug filing, trend analysis and integration with CI/CD pipelines, which are integral to the RESCALE workflow.

The adoption of SARIF has been bolstered by its support from major industry players and its integration into widely used development tools. For instance, Microsoft's Visual Studio and GitHub's code scanning features utilize SARIF [25] [46] to present static analysis results, demonstrating the format's practical applicability and industry acceptance. This widespread adoption underscores SARIF's role in promoting best practices in static analysis and enhancing software development processes.

SARIF represents a significant advancement in static analysis by providing a standardized, extensible, and interoperable format for analysis results. Its adoption within RESCALE facilitates the integration of diverse analysis tools, improves workflow efficiency, and enhances the overall quality and security of software components in the supply chain.

6.4.2 Format Details

SARIF is structured as a JSON-based format that encapsulates the results of static analysis in a standardized and extensible way. It organizes data hierarchically, ensuring clarity and ease of integration across diverse tools and platforms. The SARIF schema comprises several key components, each serving a specific role in accurately conveying the results of static analysis. These components are described below in detail:

- **version:** Identifies the version of the SARIF specification used in the report to ensure proper interpretation.
- **runs:** Represents one or more analysis executions, allowing the consolidation of outputs from different tools or repeated runs of the same tool.
- **tool:** Provides metadata about the analysis tool, including its name, version and information about its execution.
- **results:** Contains the findings from the analysis, the attributes of each result are explained below:
 - **ruleId:** Links the issue to a specific rule.
 - **message:** Describes the detected problem.
 - **locations:** Points to the precise code location or locations, including file path and line numbers.
 - **severity:** Classifies the importance of the finding (e.g, error, warning, etc.).
- **rules:** Lists the set of rules applied during the analysis, the attributes of each result are explained below:
 - **id:** The unique identifier for the rule.
 - **shortDescription:** A brief explanation of the rule.

- **fullDescription**: A detailed account of what the rule checks for.
- **helpUri**: A link to external documentation for further context.
- **invocations**: Captures details about the execution of the analysis tool, including start and end times, command-line arguments and environment variables.
- **artifacts**: Represents the files analyzed or produced during the analysis, detailing their locations, contents and roles.
- **logicalLocations**: Describes program elements like namespaces, classes or functions, aiding in pinpointing issues within the code structure.
- **taxonomies**: Defines classifications or categorizations used in the analysis, such as security vulnerability types or coding standards.

This structured approach enables SARIF to comprehensively represent static analysis results while maintaining flexibility for future extensions, ensuring its relevance in evolving software development workflows.

To further illustrate the structure and application of SARIF, two examples are provided in the appendices. The first is a simple SARIF file sourced from Microsoft’s SARIF tutorials [47], showcasing the core components and their basic structure. This example serves as a foundational reference for understanding SARIF’s standardized schema.

The second example demonstrates a SARIF file generated from the Bandit tool, which includes additional metadata and detailed analysis results. This example highlights how SARIF is used in practice within RESCALE, providing a more comprehensive view of how static analysis findings are reported and integrated into the project. These examples provide a clear and practical demonstration of SARIF’s capabilities, highlighting its role in standardizing static analysis outputs and facilitating seamless integration across diverse tools and workflows.

6.4.3 Context in RESCALE

In the RESCALE framework, SARIF is instrumental in standardizing the outputs of various static code analysis tools. Given the diverse range of analyzers employed across different programming languages and environments, SARIF offers a unified, machine-readable format that facilitates the seamless aggregation and processing of analysis results within RESCALE.

Many static analyzers integrated into RESCALE, such as bandit, flawfinder, bearer, natively support SARIF, enabling direct and consistent reporting of vulnerabilities, code quality issues and other findings. This native compatibility ensures efficient interpretation and consolidation of results across the project.

For the static code analyzers that do not inherently support SARIF, custom scripts are developed to transform the output of the tools to SARIF-compliant formats. These scripts, written mainly in Python, leverage powerful libraries such as “sarif-om” and “sarif-tools” to simplify the conversion process:

- **sarif-om**: This library provides an object model for creating and manipulating SARIF data, ensuring that the transformed outputs adhere strictly to the SARIF schema [59].

- **sarif-tools:** Offers utilities for validating and managing SARIF files, allowing for efficient handling of large and complex analysis outputs. `sarif-tools` serves a dual purpose, providing both a CLI and a library for handling SARIF files [60].

Together, these libraries enable a robust and automated workflow for converting diverse static analysis results into SARIF. This approach ensures that all static analysis data adheres to a uniform schema, promoting consistency and enhancing interoperability within the Static Code Analysis Module.

By adopting SARIF, RESCALE benefits from improved toolchain compatibility and streamlined integration. SARIF's rich metadata capabilities; including information on tool configurations, analysis rules and specific code locations, provide the necessary context for generating comprehensive reports and facilitating effective communication.

6.4.4 SARIF Validation

Ensuring the validity of SARIF files is crucial for maintaining consistency and reliability in static analysis reporting. To achieve this, we employ several validation methods described below:

- **Microsoft's SARIF Validator:** This web-based tool allows users to upload and validate SARIF files against the official SARIF schema, ensuring compliance and correctness [45].
- **NIST's SARIF Validator:** Offered by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), this validator checks SARIF files for adherence to the SARIF standard, providing an additional layer of verification [49].
- **Custom Validation Script:** We have also developed a custom Python script utilizing the "json_schema" library. This script automates the validation process by comparing SARIF files against the official SARIF JSON schema, which defines the structure and rules for valid SARIF files. The script can be seamlessly integrated into CI/CD pipelines, enabling automated SARIF validation as part of the development workflow. Moreover, the script provides detailed error reports, including specific line numbers and descriptions of validation failures.

By integrating these validation methods, we maintain the integrity and consistency of our static analysis reports, facilitating seamless integration and accurate reporting within our development workflow.

6.4.5 Challenges in Using SARIF for SSCG

While SARIF is effective for standardizing the reporting of static analysis findings, its application as an SSCG itself (and not just as 'evidence' in the SSCG) within RESCALE presents several challenges explained below:

- **Limited Scope of Analysis:** SARIF is designed specifically for static analysis results, focusing on issues such as vulnerabilities and code quality concerns. However an SSCG, requires broader assurance beyond just static analysis, including aspects like comprehensive reporting of static security guarantees, which SARIF alone cannot fulfill.
- **Lack of Standardized Vulnerability Classification:** SARIF does not enforce a uniform taxonomy for categorizing vulnerabilities. This can lead to discrepancies in how issues are classified and reported, complicating the process of assessing and comparing vulnerabilities across different components of the supply chain.
- **Integration with Other Assurance Mechanisms:** SSCG requires the integration of multiple assurance mechanisms, such as compliance checks, certification statuses and historical vulnerability data. SARIF, focused solely on static analysis, lacks inherent support for incorporating these diverse data types, limiting its ability to serve as a holistic SSCG solution.
- **Scalability Concerns:** As the size and complexity of software projects that need to be scanned increases, SARIF files can become large and unwieldy. Efficiently managing and processing these extensive reports is essential to maintain the effectiveness of SSCG within large-scale projects.

In summary, while SARIF provides a standardized format for static analysis reporting, its limitations in scope, vulnerability classification, integration with other assurance mechanisms and scalability present challenges for its use as a comprehensive SSCG within RESCALE.

6.5 SSCG Generator

The SSCG Generator, developed in Erlang for the RESCALE project, is a CLI tool designed for generating and managing SSCGs. It provides two primary subcommands: `generate` for creating SSCGs and `publish` for transmitting them. Note that the `publish` command is not fully implemented, as the overall flow of TBOM creation is currently under revision in the scope of WP4 and WP5.

The `generate` command uses an SBOM and associated test results to create an SSCG in a CDX JSON structure, as outlined in section 6.2. Additionally, the `--authors` argument captures basic producer information (name and email) in line with RESCALE's workflow requirements, with potential for adding more detailed metadata about the producer in future updates. Currently, the tool expects test reports to be simple text files. However, it is desirable to adopt a standardized, machine-processable format such as SARIF and the SSCG Generator will support it in the future.

The following shows the help texts of the tool which illustrate the usage:

Main Help

```
% sscg_generator --help
usage: sscg_generator {generate|publish} [-v] [--verbose]
```

Subcommands:

<code>generate</code>	Generate an SSCG using an SBOM and metadata files
<code>publish</code>	Send the SSCG and the input SBOM to a URL

Optional arguments:

`-v, --verbose` control verbosity level (max `-vv`)

Generate Command Help

```
% sscg_generator generate --help
```

```
usage: sscg_generator generate [-v] [-s <SBOM_file>] [-t <test_folder>] ...
```

Mandatory arguments:

<code>-s, --sbom</code>	SBOM JSON file path
<code>-t, --test</code>	Test folder path

Optional arguments:

<code>-o, --output</code>	Output file path and name
<code>-a, --authors</code>	Specify producer information in the format: name:email
<code>-v, --verbose</code>	control verbosity level (max <code>-vv</code>)

Publish Command Help

```
% sscg_generator publish --help
```

```
usage: sscg_generator publish [-v] [-s <SBOM_file>] [-g <SSCG_file>] ...
```

Optional arguments:

<code>-s, --sbom</code>	SBOM JSON file path
<code>-g, --sscg</code>	SSCG file path
<code>-e, --endpoint</code>	Endpoint URL where to send the files
<code>-v, --verbose</code>	control verbosity level (max <code>-vv</code>)

The SSCG Generator is an essential part of the static code analysis module and will be integrated to automatically trigger after testing efforts conclude, streamlining SSCG generation within the RESCALE workflow. At present, any form of trust assurance, such as signatures for parts of the SSCG or proof of computation with respect to the executed tests, is absent from the tool, as further research is required to define appropriate methods for embedding these assurances. Further the TBOM concept envisions to support an access right system such that later on parts of the e.g. published SSCG can be adjusted by entities with proper permissions. The foundation for such a system might affect the generation of the SSCG itself and is, as the trust assurance, subject to further research.

In future updates, the tool may also incorporate authentication tokens and TBOM creation contexts based on the finalized structure of the TBOM creation flow.

7 Main Innovations & Conclusion

This section summarizes the key contributions of this deliverable and outlines any future work that will be undertaken as the RESCALE project advances.

7.1 Main Innovations

RESCALE introduces the first application of ML/DL-based static analysis to the Erlang ecosystem through CodeBERT and SAVE-ME, advancing vulnerability and weakness detection in a language known for its concurrency and message-passing complexities. The project also targets the first real-world deployment of DetectEr, a formal verification tool using Hennessy–Milner Logic to validate execution traces and ensure safety properties in Erlang systems. SASTer introduces a transformative approach to static code analysis by unifying multiple open-source tools within a modular framework. Its use of docker based isolation ensures consistency and compatibility across diverse environments, while using SARIF streamlines vulnerability reporting and integration with CI/CD pipelines. SASTer’s extensibility and planned ML/DL integration for reducing false positives and prioritizing vulnerabilities highlight its forward-thinking design. Complementing this, the Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE) leverages symbolic execution through the Angr framework to detect binary-level vulnerabilities, offering unique capabilities for analyzing compiled code and prioritizing critical issues through control flow analysis.

The design of the Static Code Analysis Module in RESCALE enables comprehensive security assessments by integrating advanced tools and methodologies. A cornerstone of this design is the Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG), which consolidates static analysis results into a unified format. By leveraging SARIF, the SSCG ensures compatibility with industry standards, streamlining the reporting of vulnerabilities and weaknesses.

7.2 Conclusion

The RESCALE project has laid a robust foundation for supply chain security through its Static Code Analysis Module, which integrates advanced ML/DL-driven vulnerability and weakness detection alongside formal verification techniques across languages such as Python, C/C++, and Erlang. Central to this framework is the Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG), a CycloneDX-compatible report that unifies testing outputs, supporting the creation of a comprehensive Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM).

Key ongoing challenges include refining detection accuracy, reducing false positives, and enhancing interoperability among diverse tools and reporting formats. To address these, RESCALE is integrating SARIF for consistent testing output, streamlining SSCG compatibility, and collaborating with stakeholders to ensure broader SBOM standardization. As these efforts progress, RESCALE’s static code analysis framework aims to become a scalable, automated solution for comprehensive supply chain security.

7.3 Future Work

While significant progress has been made in developing the static code analysis framework within RESCALE, substantial refinement and further implementation are required to achieve the project's goals. Key components of the static analysis module still need large development effort to enhance accuracy, reduce false positives, and improve integration with the broader RESCALE workflow. The following paragraphs outline and recap specific challenges and areas where additional work is needed to realize a fully functional and robust analysis framework.

7.3.1 Identified Challenges

One of the primary challenges for enhancing static analysis tools is the lack of an open-source dataset containing labeled Erlang functions with their associated vulnerabilities. Since no such dataset currently exists, the project is in the process of creating one based on Infer, aimed at multiclass classification. The specific vulnerability classes to be included are still under discussion to ensure comprehensive coverage of common security issues in Erlang.

Another significant challenge is the high false positive rate, a common issue in static analysis tools. To address this, an Erlang expert will curate and filter the dataset to ensure the accuracy of vulnerability labels, minimizing false positives in the ground truth data. Additionally, leveraging LLM and using diverse datasets from different Erlang projects allows the model to generalize better than traditional static code analyzers. This approach enhances the model's ability to distinguish actual vulnerabilities from benign code patterns, thus reducing the rate of false positives and improving the overall reliability of vulnerability detection.

RefactorErl is a valuable tool within RESCALE for static analysis and refactoring in Erlang. However, it faces several usability challenges. As RefactorErl is currently maintained in a private repository and lacks compatibility with recent Erlang versions, the tool is underutilized despite its potential to enhance analysis workflows. RESCALE, specifically the partner PST, is addressing these limitations by initiating a migration of RefactorErl to a public repository, increasing its accessibility, and engaging with stakeholders to make its advanced features available to the community.

The Erlang ecosystem currently lacks a solid foundation for Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) generation, with minimal support for the CycloneDX format, making dependency tracking and vulnerability analysis challenging. Additionally, there is limited integration of Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) and Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) standards, leading to insufficient visibility of known vulnerabilities in Erlang libraries. These gaps hinder RESCALE's ability to automate vulnerability management and integrate Erlang components into standardized security workflows. Addressing these limitations will be essential to enhance Erlang's compatibility with broader supply chain security standards.

A significant challenge in RESCALE is the inconsistent output formats from static analyzers like Infer (which is utilized with CodeBERT), which produces unique, non-standard formats rather than the industry-standard SARIF. This inconsistency hampers automation efforts, as each tool's output requires custom parsing for integration into workflows, limiting scalability. For languages like Erlang, which lacks strong SBOM and vulnerability support, this issue is compounded by the absence of CVE and CWE mappings, making it harder to classify

and prioritize detected issues. Addressing this challenge will require either adapting existing tools to support SARIF or creating parsers to translate custom outputs, while also encouraging CVE/CWE integration to improve compatibility with vulnerability databases.

7.3.2 Possible Mitigations & Improvements

A key area for future improvement is addressing the underrepresentation of Erlang in CodeBERT's training data. Currently, CodeBERT was pre-trained on a limited selection of programming languages, which affects its ability to fully capture the unique features and nuances of Erlang. To improve the model's performance, it is essential to include more Erlang-specific data or consider alternative models better suited to the language.

One direction is to explore the use of StarCoder [41], a large language model trained on a more diverse set of programming languages. StarCoder's broader training data could provide better support for Erlang-specific syntax and patterns, enhancing vulnerability detection. However, StarCoder's size also introduces its own challenges, as it requires significantly more computational resources to deploy and fine-tune. Balancing model performance with resource constraints will be a key consideration in exploring this approach.

RefactorErl presents significant potential for enhancing static analysis and refactoring capabilities within the RESCALE framework, particularly for Erlang codebases. Although current limitations, such as repository accessibility and version compatibility, have hindered its immediate integration, efforts are underway to resolve these issues. Once these challenges are addressed, RefactorErl is expected to be incorporated into the RESCALE toolchain, providing advanced code structure analysis and refactoring support.

PST is further working on enhancing CycloneDX support within the Erlang ecosystem to address current SBOM limitations. This involves developing tools and integrations that enable more comprehensive SBOM generation, aligned with CycloneDX standards. Additionally, RESCALE is collaborating closely with maintainers of key Erlang libraries to establish a unified SBOM library, aiming to provide broad and standardized SBOM support across the ecosystem. First large efforts have been made here (which are already integrated into the static code analysis module) leading to further discussions on a final design of a SBOM library.

Future work for DetectEr involves configuring IoT devices to generate detailed execution traces for verifying software update mechanisms against defined safety properties. This requires modifications to device firmware to enable comprehensive trace capture, down to the level of data blocks written to hard drives. Such an in-depth setup ensures that DetectEr can monitor the entire update process accurately, addressing the complex requirements of verifying secure and reliable software updates in IoT environments.

Appendices

A SSCG Example

```
{
  "bomFormat": "CycloneDX",
  "specVersion": "1.6",
  "serialNumber": "urn:uuid:b4f2954f-a96d-4578-9509-1ae2d6476209",
  "metadata": {
    "timestamp": "2024-08-13T01:28:52.765Z",
    "authors": [
      {
        "name": "Some Company that wants to generate a SSCG for their
          library",
        "email": "some@company.com"
      }
    ],
    "tools": {
      "components": [
        {
          "type": "application",
          "name": "ReSCALE SSCG Generator",
          "version": "1.4.17",
          "description": "A ReSCALE certified tool to generate SSCGs",
          "purl": "pkg:hex/sscg-generator@1.4.17",
          "data": [
            {
              "name": "CLI configuration flags",
              "type": "configuration",
              "contents": {
                "attachment": {
                  "content": "--test-report=report.json
                    --output=sscg.json"
                }
              }
            }
          ],
          "hashes": [
            {
              "alg": "SHA-1",
              "content": "2fd4e1c67a2d28fced849ee1bb76e7391b93eb12"
            }
          ]
        }
      ],
      {
        "type": "container",
        "name": "ReSCALE Static Code Analysis Module",
        "version": "2.1.7",
        "description": "A ReSCALE certified container to execute
          static testing",
        "purl": "pkg:docker/static-code-analysis-module@2.1.7",
        "data": [
          {
            "name": "Docker Environment",
            "type": "configuration",
            "contents": {
              "attachment": {
                "content": "RESCALE_STATIC_ANALYSIS_LANG=erlang
                  \nRESCALE_DRY_RUN=false"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

```

    }
  }
],
"hashes": [
  {
    "alg": "SHA-1",
    "content": "35d1c8f259129dc800ec8e073bb68f995424619c"
  }
]
}
}],
"definitions": {
  "standards": [
    {
      "bom-ref": "https://rescale-project.eu/standard/1.0.0",
      "name": "The ReSCALE Standard",
      "description": "The ReSCALE Standard describes a workflow to
        create a Trusted BOM (TBOM)",
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "requirements": [
        {
          "bom-ref":
            "https://rescale-project.eu/standard/1.0.0/conformance/complete",
          "identifier": "rescale/1.0.0/conformance/complete",
          "title": "Full conformance with ReSCALEs 'complete'
            profile, e.g. complete absence of findings"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
},
"declarations": {
  "targets": {
    "components": [
      {
        "type": "library",
        "name": "A Very Nice Library which was tested by the ReSCALE
          Static Code Analysis Module",
        "bom-ref": "pkg:hex/a-very-nice-library@1.0.0",
        "version": "1.0.0",
        "description": "Such a good piece of software, but it has
          security issues ...",
        "purl": "pkg:hex/a-very-nice-library@1.0.0",
        "hashes": [
          {
            "alg": "SHA-1",
            "content": "53ab2f0f92e87ea4874c8c6997335c211d81e636"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
},
"assessors": [
  {
    "bom-ref": "Producer Reference",

```

```

    "thirdParty": false,
    "organization": {
      "bom-ref": "Producer Entity",
      "name": "Some Company that wants to generate a SSCG for
        their library",
      "contact": [
        {
          "email": "some@company.com"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "attestations": [
    {
      "assessor": "Producer Reference",
      "summary": "Mapping of Requirements to Claims",
      "map": [
        {
          "requirement":
            "https://rescale-project.eu/standard/1.0.0/conformance/complete",
          "counterClaims": [
            "Claim: ReSCALE Test Suite XY found something!"
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "claims": [
    {
      "bom-ref": "Claim: ReSCALE Test Suite XY found something!",
      "target": "pkg:hex/a-very-nice-library@1.0.0",
      "evidence": [
        "Evidence: memory error"
      ]
    }
  ],
  "evidence": [
    {
      "bom-ref": "Evidence: memory error",
      "description": "Exploitable memory error found",
      "data": [
        {
          "name": "ReSCALE Test Suite XY Output",
          "contents": {
            "attachment": {
              "content": "Test Suite XY found: \n\tmemory corruption
                in file main.c at line 23"
            }
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

B SARIF Examples

B.1 Simple Example

```
{
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "$schema": "http://json.schemastore.org/sarif-2.1.0-rtm.4",
  "runs": [
    {
      "tool": {
        "driver": {
          "name": "ESLint",
          "informationUri": "https://eslint.org",
          "rules": [
            {
              "id": "no-unused-vars",
              "shortDescription": {
                "text": "disallow unused variables"
              },
              "helpUri":
                "https://eslint.org/docs/rules/no-unused-vars",
              "properties": {
                "category": "Variables"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      },
      "artifacts": [
        {
          "location": {
            "uri":
              "file:///C:/dev/sarif/sarif-tutorials/samples/Introduction/simple-ex
          }
        }
      ],
      "results": [
        {
          "level": "error",
          "message": {
            "text": "'x' is assigned a value but never used."
          },
          "locations": [
            {
              "physicalLocation": {
                "artifactLocation": {
                  "uri":
                    "file:///C:/dev/sarif/sarif-tutorials/samples/Introduction/simp
                "index": 0
              },
              "region": {
                "startLine": 1,
                "startColumn": 5
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    ],
    "ruleId": "no-unused-vars",
    "ruleIndex": 0
  }
]
}
]
}

```

B.2 SAVE-ME Example

```

{
  "$schema": "https://json.schemastore.org/sarif-2.1.0",
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "runs": [
    {
      "tool": {
        "driver": {
          "name": "Erlang Analyzer",
          "fullName": "Erlang Vulnerability Analyzer",
          "version": "1.0.0",
          "informationUri": "https://sample_site.com",
          "rules": [
            {
              "id": "vulnerability-detection",
              "name": "Vulnerability Detection",
              "fullDescription": {
                "text": "Detects vulnerabilities in Erlang functions"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      },
      "results": [
        {
          "ruleId": "vulnerability-detection",
          "message": {
            "text": "No vulnerability detected with confidence 3.59.
              Confidence for potential vulnerability: -3.28."
          },
          "locations": [
            {
              "physicalLocation": {
                "artifactLocation": {
                  "uri": "file:///Users/Shared/Files From
                    d.localized/Materijali/_RESCALE/save-me/test_dir/sample_erlang
                },
                "region": {
                  "startLine": 19,
                  "endLine": 19
                }
              }
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          "properties": {

```

```

        "confidence": 3.586867332458496
      },
    ],
    {
      "ruleId": "vulnerability-detection",
      "message": {
        "text": "No vulnerability detected with confidence 3.59.
          Confidence for potential vulnerability: -3.30."
      },
      "locations": [
        {
          "physicalLocation": {
            "artifactLocation": {
              "uri": "file:///Users/Shared/Files From
                d.localized/Materijali/_RESCALE/save-me/test_dir/sample_erlang
            },
            "region": {
              "startLine": 26,
              "endLine": 26
            }
          }
        }
      ],
      "properties": {
        "confidence": 3.591543436050415
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

B.3 Bandit Example

```

{
  "$schema": "https://json.schemastore.org/sarif-2.1.0.json",
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "runs": [
    {
      "tool": {
        "driver": {
          "name": "Bandit",
          "organization": "PyCQA",
          "rules": [
            {
              "id": "B404",
              "name": "blacklist",
              "properties": {
                "tags": [
                  "security",
                  "external/cwe/cwe-78"
                ],
                "precision": "high"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

```
    "helpUri":
      "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/blacklist_impo
  },
  {
    "id": "B602",
    "name": "subprocess_popen_with_shell_equals_true",
    "properties": {
      "tags": [
        "security",
        "external/cwe/cwe-78"
      ],
      "precision": "high"
    },
    "helpUri":
      "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b602_subprocess_p
  },
  {
    "id": "B608",
    "name": "hardcoded_sql_expressions",
    "properties": {
      "tags": [
        "security",
        "external/cwe/cwe-89"
      ],
      "precision": "low"
    },
    "helpUri":
      "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b608_hardcoded_sq
  },
  {
    "id": "B201",
    "name": "flask_debug_true",
    "properties": {
      "tags": [
        "security",
        "external/cwe/cwe-94"
      ],
      "precision": "medium"
    },
    "helpUri":
      "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b201_flask_debug_
  },
  {
    "id": "B403",
    "name": "blacklist",
    "properties": {
      "tags": [
        "security",
        "external/cwe/cwe-502"
      ],
      "precision": "high"
    },
    "helpUri":
      "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/blacklist_impo
  },
  {
    "id": "B324",
    "name": "hashlib",
```

```
        "properties": {
          "tags": [
            "security",
            "external/cwe/cwe-327"
          ],
          "precision": "high"
        },
        "helpUri":
          "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b324_hashlib.html"
      },
      {
        "id": "B105",
        "name": "hardcoded_password_string",
        "properties": {
          "tags": [
            "security",
            "external/cwe/cwe-259"
          ],
          "precision": "medium"
        },
        "helpUri":
          "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b105_hardcoded_pa"
      },
      {
        "id": "B301",
        "name": "blacklist",
        "properties": {
          "tags": [
            "security",
            "external/cwe/cwe-502"
          ],
          "precision": "high"
        },
        "helpUri":
          "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/blacklist_call"
      },
      {
        "id": "B113",
        "name": "request_without_timeout",
        "properties": {
          "tags": [
            "security",
            "external/cwe/cwe-400"
          ],
          "precision": "low"
        },
        "helpUri":
          "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b113_request_with"
      }
    ],
    "version": "1.7.10",
    "semanticVersion": "1.7.10"
  }
},
"invocations": [
  {
    "executionSuccessful": true,
    "endTimeUtc": "2024-10-01T08:35:40Z",
```

```
"toolConfigurationNotifications": [
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "syntax error while parsing AST from file"
    },
    "level": "error",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri":
              "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_1.py"
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  }
],
"properties": {
  "metrics": {
    "_totals": {
      "loc": 139,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "SEVERITY.LOW": 4,
      "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 2,
      "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 3,
      "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 2,
      "SEVERITY.HIGH": 4,
      "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 7
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_1.py": {
      "loc": 56,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_2.py": {
      "loc": 14,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "SEVERITY.LOW": 1,
      "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 0,
      "SEVERITY.HIGH": 1,
      "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 2
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_3.py": {
      "loc": 28,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
```

```

    "SEVERITY.LOW": 0,
    "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
    "SEVERITY.HIGH": 1,
    "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 1,
    "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 1,
    "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 0
  },
  "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4.py": {
    "loc": 22,
    "nosec": 0,
    "skipped_tests": 0,
    "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
    "SEVERITY.LOW": 3,
    "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
    "SEVERITY.HIGH": 2,
    "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 1,
    "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 5
  },
  "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_5.py": {
    "loc": 19,
    "nosec": 0,
    "skipped_tests": 0,
    "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
    "SEVERITY.LOW": 0,
    "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
    "SEVERITY.HIGH": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 1,
    "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 0,
    "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 0
  }
}
},
"results": [
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "Consider possible security implications
              associated with the subprocess module."
    },
    "level": "note",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": "import subprocess\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 18,
            "endLine": 1,
            "startColumn": 1,
            "startLine": 1
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri":
              "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_2.

```

```

    },
    "contextRegion": {
      "snippet": {
        "text": "import subprocess\n\ndef
          list_files(directory):\n"
      },
      "endLine": 3,
      "startLine": 1
    }
  }
},
],
"properties": {
  "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
  "issue_severity": "LOW"
},
"ruleId": "B404",
"ruleIndex": 0
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "subprocess call with shell=True identified,
      security issue."
  },
  "level": "error",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "          result =
              subprocess.check_output(command, shell=True)\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 62,
          "endLine": 8,
          "startColumn": 18,
          "startLine": 8
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri":
            "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_2."
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "          command = \"ls
              { }\".format(directory)\n          result =
              subprocess.check_output(command, shell=True)\n
              print(result.decode())\n"
          },
          "endLine": 9,
          "startLine": 7
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
  }
}

```

```

    },
    "ruleId": "B602",
    "ruleIndex": 1
  },
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "Possible SQL injection vector through
              string-based query construction."
    },
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": "      query = f\"SELECT * FROM users WHERE
                      username = '{username}'\"\\n\\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 65,
            "endLine": 24,
            "startColumn": 13,
            "startLine": 24
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri":
              "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_3."
          },
          "contextRegion": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": "      username =
                      request.args.get('username')\\n      query =
                      f\"SELECT * FROM users WHERE username =
                      '{username}'\"\\n      \\n"
            },
            "endLine": 25,
            "startLine": 23
          }
        }
      }
    ],
    "properties": {
      "issue_confidence": "LOW",
      "issue_severity": "MEDIUM"
    },
    "ruleId": "B608",
    "ruleIndex": 2
  },
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "A Flask app appears to be run with debug=True,
              which exposes the Werkzeug debugger and allows the
              execution of arbitrary code."
    },
    "level": "error",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {

```

```

        "text": "    app.run(debug=True)\n"
    },
    "endColumn": 24,
    "endLine": 36,
    "startColumn": 5,
    "startLine": 36
  },
  "artifactLocation": {
    "uri":
      "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_3."
  },
  "contextRegion": {
    "snippet": {
      "text": "    init_db()\n    app.run(debug=True)\n"
    },
    "endLine": 36,
    "startLine": 35
  }
}
]
},
"properties": {
  "issue_confidence": "MEDIUM",
  "issue_severity": "HIGH"
},
"ruleId": "B201",
"ruleIndex": 3
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Consider possible security implications
      associated with the subprocess module."
  },
  "level": "note",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import subprocess\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 18,
          "endLine": 1,
          "startColumn": 1,
          "startLine": 1
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri":
            "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import subprocess\nimport os\nimport
              hashlib\n"
          },
          "endLine": 3,
          "startLine": 1
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

```

    }
  }
],
"properties": {
  "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
  "issue_severity": "LOW"
},
"ruleId": "B404",
"ruleIndex": 0
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Consider possible security implications
associated with pickle module."
  },
  "level": "note",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import pickle\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 14,
          "endLine": 4,
          "startColumn": 1,
          "startLine": 4
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri":
            "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import hashlib\nimport pickle\n\n"
          },
          "endLine": 5,
          "startLine": 3
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "LOW"
  },
  "ruleId": "B403",
  "ruleIndex": 4
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "subprocess call with shell=True identified,
security issue."
  },
  "level": "error",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {

```

```

        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "        subprocess.call(user_input,
              shell=True)\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 44,
          "endLine": 8,
          "startColumn": 5,
          "startLine": 8
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri":
            "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "def dangerous_function(user_input):\n
              subprocess.call(user_input, shell=True)\n\n"
          },
          "endLine": 9,
          "startLine": 7
        }
      }
    ],
    "properties": {
      "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
      "issue_severity": "HIGH"
    },
    "ruleId": "B602",
    "ruleIndex": 1
  },
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "Use of weak MD5 hash for security. Consider
        usedforsecurity=False"
    },
    "level": "error",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": "        return
                hashlib.md5(password.encode('utf-8')).hexdigest()\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 49,
            "endLine": 12,
            "startColumn": 12,
            "startLine": 12
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri":
              "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
          },
          "contextRegion": {
            "snippet": {

```

```

        "text": "def weak_hash(password):\n    return\n        hashlib.md5(password.encode('utf-8')).hexdigest()\n\n",
        "endLine": 13,
        "startLine": 11
    }
}
],
"properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
},
"ruleId": "B324",
"ruleIndex": 5
},
{
    "message": {
        "text": "Possible hardcoded password: 'my_secret_key'"
    },
    "level": "note",
    "locations": [
        {
            "physicalLocation": {
                "region": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "SECRET_KEY = \"my_secret_key\"\n"
                    },
                    "endColumn": 29,
                    "endLine": 15,
                    "startColumn": 14,
                    "startLine": 15
                },
                "artifactLocation": {
                    "uri":
                        "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
                },
                "contextRegion": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "# Vulnerability: Hardcoded secret\nkey\nSECRET_KEY = \"my_secret_key\"\n\n"
                    },
                    "endLine": 16,
                    "startLine": 14
                }
            }
        }
    ],
    "properties": {
        "issue_confidence": "MEDIUM",
        "issue_severity": "LOW"
    },
    "ruleId": "B105",
    "ruleIndex": 6
},
{
    "message": {

```

```

        "text": "Pickle and modules that wrap it can be unsafe
                when used to deserialize untrusted data, possible
                security issue."
    },
    "locations": [
        {
            "physicalLocation": {
                "region": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "        return pickle.loads(data)\n"
                    },
                    "endColumn": 30,
                    "endLine": 19,
                    "startColumn": 12,
                    "startLine": 19
                },
                "artifactLocation": {
                    "uri":
                        "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4."
                },
                "contextRegion": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "def insecure_deserialization(data):\n
                                return pickle.loads(data)\n\n"
                    },
                    "endLine": 20,
                    "startLine": 18
                }
            }
        }
    ],
    "properties": {
        "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
        "issue_severity": "MEDIUM"
    },
    "ruleId": "B301",
    "ruleIndex": 7
},
{
    "message": {
        "text": "Call to requests without timeout"
    },
    "locations": [
        {
            "physicalLocation": {
                "region": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "        response =
                                requests.post(\"http://insecure-server.com/api/data\",
                                                json=data)\n"
                    },
                    "endColumn": 79,
                    "endLine": 15,
                    "startColumn": 16,
                    "startLine": 15
                },
                "artifactLocation": {

```

```
        "uri":
          "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_5.
    },
    "contextRegion": {
      "snippet": {
        "text": "def send_data(data):\n    response =
                requests.post(\"http://insecure-server.com/api/data\",
                               json=data)\n    return response\n"
      },
      "endLine": 16,
      "startLine": 14
    }
  }
],
"properties": {
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